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Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as olfactory attractant and enhancer for the efficiency of protein-based baits to attract *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae) under field conditions

Nabil, M. Ghanim; Ahmed, Ramadan El-Rokh and Salma, K. Ragab

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

The Mediterranean fruit fly (MFF) *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is considered the most economically important pest attacking many fruit hosts. The present study was conducted under field conditions of a mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) orchard in Dakahlia Governorate, Egypt aiming to evaluate di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an olfactory attractant for adults of MFF and evaluate its efficiency as an enhancer for the commercial product of the protein-based bait (Buminal). The obtained results showed that the efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an attractant to MFF adults increased as its concentration increased till it reached the range between 3.0 and 3.5%, and then its efficiency decreased with the increase in concentration. The statistical relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as an attractant to MFF was evaluated. Concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate attracted females obviously more than males. On another hand, adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with concentrations of 1 and 2% to Buminal increased its efficiency as an attractant to MFF adults with 1.46 and 2.86 folds of the efficiency of Buminal alone.

Introduction

Citrus fruits host many pests worldwide and fruit flies of the family Tephritidae are of these pests (Onah *et al.*, 2015). Tephritid fruit flies are recognized as major insect pests in horticultural and vegetable orchards causing large losses of fruits (Allwood, 1997). The Mediterranean fruit fly (MFF), *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is considered one of the most economically important pests attacking many fruit hosts

(Liquido *et al.*, 1991 and Ghanim and Moustafa, 2009). It is one of the quarantine important pest species because of its extensive damage to a wide range of cultivated and wild fruit and vegetable crops (FAO and IAEA, 2013). The larvae of MFF devour into the fruits' pulp causing great damage and making fruits unfavorable for exportation or marketing (White and Elson-Harris, 1992 and Borge and Basedow, 1997). According to Sayed *et al.* (1970), Pena *et al.* (1998), Ghanim and

Moustafa (2009) and Papadopoulos *et al.* (2015) reported that MFF causes considerable damage in many fruit species.

As a result of the lack of an effective female attractant; several studies had been done to examine some odors as lures for attracting female of fruit flies such as ammonium compounds. According to Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014), Ghanim (2018), Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021); ammonium compounds play significant roles in attracting tephritid fruit flies.

Where Piñero *et al.* (2011) mentioned that ammonia-releasing substances could be developed as effective synthetic food-based lures for fruit flies; however, females of tephritid flies require protein sources for egg production and ammonia plays a role in locating protein-food sources (Piñero *et al.*, 2015 and 2017). Also, ammonium compounds could be used for enhancing some protein-based baits for attracting adults of MFF and *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Hemeida *et al.*, 2017; El-Metwally, 2017 and Ghanim and El-Metwally, 2019). While Ragab and Youssef (2021) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021) used ammonium compounds (*i.e.* Ammonium acetate and di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate) to activate each other (As attractants for MFF and *B. zonata*) by mixing them together at different ratios of each.

The present study is aimed to evaluate di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an olfactory attractant for adults of MFF at different concentrations in addition to evaluating it as an enhancer for the commercial product of the protein-based bait (Buminal) to increase its attractiveness to adults of MFF under field conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Chemicals:

Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate ((NH₄)₂HPO₄) was obtained from Edwic Company, Egypt. Buminal (39.78%) was obtained from Horticultural Insect Pests Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute.

2. Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as olfactory attractant for the Mediterranean fruit fly:

Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate was tested as olfactory attractants for MFF, *C. capitata* under field conditions of mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) orchard (about 5 feddans = 21000 m²) located at Mansoura district, Dakahlia governorate, Egypt (the experimental farm of Faculty of Agriculture, Mansoura University). The four concentrations 1, 2, 3 (which is the recommended concentration) and 5% as w: v of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate: water was used inside the modified Nadel traps that were described by Hanafy *et al.* (2001) during the period from the 13th till 28th of October 2022.

Each concentration of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (250 ml) was put in one trap and repeated four times. Traps were distributed in a completely randomized design in the previously mentioned orchard and hung in a shaded place of the trees at a height of about 1.5 meters from the ground on the trees within the wind direction. To prevent interference among the traps, there had to be at least 20 meters between each pair of hanging traps.

Every 3 days (As an interval period), traps were inspected over a period of 15 days by filtering the solutions from MFF adults and returned to the traps again without renewing the solution. Captured MFF females and males were counted and recorded as calculated FTD values (Captured flies /trap/day).

3. Enhancement of protein-based bait by di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to attract Mediterranean fruit fly:

Buminal (The commercial product of the protein-based bait as hydrolyzed protein 39.78%) was prepared at the concentration of 5% (v/v) by diluting with distilled water. The mixture of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and Buminal 5% was prepared. Each one liter of Buminal 5% was mixed with 10 g of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to obtain 1% (w/v) or mixed with 20 g to obtain 2% concentration. The prepared mixtures were compared with Buminal 5% alone as a positive control. Each mixture (250 ml) was put inside the modified Nadel traps and repeated four times.

In the previously mentioned mandarin orchard, experiments were carried out during the period from the 24th of November to 9th of December 2022. The prepared traps were distributed in the orchard as previously mentioned. After hanging the traps, they were checked every three days (as an interval period) for a total of 15 days. As indicated before, both male

Table (1): Efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations (Conc.) as attractants for Mediterranean fruit fly adults during 15 days in mandarin orchard.

Conc.	FTD after (In days)					LSD(P=5%)
	3	6	9	12	15	
0.5%	0.25±0.16	0.41±0.31	0.90±0.31	1.08±0.42	0.66±0.47	0.53
1%	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	1.33±0.47	1.25±0.31	0.25±0.16	0.39
2%	0.17±0.09	0.17±0.09	0.17±0.09	0.33±0.00	0.94±0.19	0.25
3%	0.17±0.09	0.17±0.09	5.66±0.81	5.99±0.94	2.75±0.50	0.92
5%	0.17±0.09	0.25±0.16	0.41±0.20	1.83±0.33	1.41±0.41	0.48
LSD(P=5%)	0.24	0.30	0.73	0.76	0.56	0.80

Figure (1) shows the general means of attracting MFF to di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations all over 15 days. This figure showed that the concentration of 3% was the significantly highest effective

and female caught files were counted and recovered.

4. Statistical analysis:

One-way ANOVA was used to analyze the obtained data followed by the least significant difference (L.S.D) at a probability level of 5%. In addition, regression analysis was performed. CoHort Software (2004) was used to perform all analyses.

Results and discussion

1. Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as olfactory attractant for Mediterranean fruit fly:

Data represented in Table (1) showed that the highest activity of 0.5, 3 and 5% concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate was recorded after 12 days (FTDs were 1.08±0.42, 5.99±0.94 and 1.83±0.33, respectively); while the highest activity of 1 and 2% concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate was recorded after 9 and 15 days (FTDs were 1.33±0.47 and 0.94±0.19). On another hand, the highest activity of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate after 9, 12 and 15 days were recorded at the concentration of 3%.

concentration as an attractant for MFF adults, while the significantly lowest concentration was of 2%. The concentrations of 0.5, 1 and 5% showed moderate ranks as attractants for MFF adults.

Figure (1): General mean of attracted MFF adults (as FTDs) to di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations during 15 days in mandarin orchard (Columns had the same letters did not differ at the significantly of 5%).

The relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as an attractant to MFF was illustrated in Figure (2). As shown in this figure, it can be noticed that the efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate increased as its concentration increased till it reached the range between 3.0 and 3.5%. After that the efficiency of di-

ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an attractant to MFF decreased with the increase of its concentration.

The statistical relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as attractant to MFF was evaluated as follow:

$$FTD = -0.23 C^2 + 1.42 C - 0.42$$

Figure (2): The relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as attractant to Mediterranean fruit fly in mandarin orchard.

Sex ratios of the attracted MFF adults to the tested concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate were evaluated and illustrated in Figure (3). The highest number of females per one male was recorded with a concentration 5% (9.12 females/one male)

followed by the di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentration of 1% (8.00 females). The general mean sex ratio in all of the tested di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations reached 5.57 females per one male.

Figure (3): Sex ratios of the attracted Mediterranean fruit fly adults to the tested concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate in mandarin orchard.

As shown in Figure (4), the efficiency of all the tested di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations increased by the passed time; however, each passed day increased the attracted MFF adults (As FTDs) by 0.05, 0.06, 0.06, 0.37 and 0.14 individuals when used 0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5%

concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate, respectively. So, the relative stability showed that a 3% concentration of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate was the most effective concentration to attract MFF adults.

Figure (4): Stability of the tested concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as attractants for Mediterranean fruit fly adults against time all over 15 days in mandarin orchard.

2. Enhancement of protein-based bait by di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to attract Mediterranean fruit fly:

Data represented in Figure (5) shows that adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 1% to the food attractant (Buminal 5%) increased its efficiency as an attractant to MFF by 5.76 times more than Buminal alone after three days of hanging the traps. At all of the other inspections (6, 9, 12 and 15

days) there were no significant differences between adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 1% to Buminal and Buminal alone. When adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 2% to Buminal, it increased Buminal's efficiency as an attractant to MFF by 8.74, 5.55, 1.78, 2.55 and 1.61 times in comparison with Buminal alone after 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days of hanging traps, respectively.

Figure (5): Enhancement of protein-based bait (Buminal) by using 1 and 2% concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to attract Mediterranean fruit fly all over 15 days in mandarin orchard.

As general, adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with concentrations of 1 and 2% to Buminal increased its efficiency as an attractant to MFF adults with 1.46 and 2.86 folds of the efficiency of Buminal alone all over the tested period (Figure 6).

Figure(6): Mean FTDs of attracted Mediterranean fruit fly to protein-based bait (Buminal) alone or enhanced with 1 and 2% concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate all over the tested period (15 days) in mandarin orchard (Columns had the same letters did not differ at the significantly of 5%).

Figure (7) shows that Buminal alone or enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 1% were more stable against the passed time after hanging traps; however, each passed day increased their efficiency as attractants to MFF by 0.11 and 0.02 adults per trap per day. With respect to Buminal which was enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 2%, it was relatively less stable against the passed time; however, each passed day decreased the recorded FTDs of MFF by 0.02 adults.

Figure (7): Stability of Buminal alone or enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 1 and 2% as attractants for MFF adults against time all over 15 days in mandarin orchard.

Nitrogen sources dietary has a very strong influence on the behavior and physiology of fruit flies (Hemeida *et al.*, 2017 and Ghanim and El-Metwally, 2019). According to the role of ammonia in fruit fly attraction, we can increase the efficiency of fruit fly attractants by changing the formulations of variety of baits including ammonia such as ammonium acetate has been shown to be the most attractive component of food attractant (Biolure) for MFF (Leblanc *et al.*, 2010). Also, Ghanim (2018) reported significant effects of adding ammonium acetate and di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to GF-120; however, there were significant positive relationships obtained between relative amounts of ammonium compounds in the bait and the numbers of attracted *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae), *B. zonata* and MFF. The production of ammonia because of protein bacterial degradation was correlated with increases in bait efficiency as an attractant to females of fruit flies (Bateman and Morton, 1981). As well as low attractiveness of proteinaceous baits to MFF was associated with low release rates of ammonia and vice versa (Mazor, 2009). The range of attractiveness of fruit flies to ammonia-based compounds is very narrow, while the range of repellence is much wider (Bateman and Morton, 1981 and Mazor *et al.*, 2002). The present results showed that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate exhibited a good efficiency in attracting MFF at concentrations ranging between 3.0 and 3.5%. The lower efficiency of lower concentrations is probably due to their lower attractiveness to MFF adults; while, the lower efficiency of higher concentrations may be due to their repellent action to MFF adults.

Similar results were obtained by Ragab and Youssef (2021) who reported that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at its concentration of 3% was superior to its concentrations in attracting MFF in guava

and mandarin orchards. While Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021) found that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at its concentrations of 1 and 2% were superior of its concentrations in attracting *B. zonata* under field conditions. In another hand, adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 2% to the commercially protein-based bait of Buminal significantly increased Buminal's efficiency as an attractant for MFF adults.

Similar results were reported by Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019) that adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at its concentrations of 2 and 3% to Buminal significantly increased its efficiency as an attractant to MFF under field conditions. Also, El-Metwally (2017) and Ghanim (2018) found that the insecticidal bait (GF-120; which considered a protein-based bait) can be enhanced by di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 2% to increase its efficiency as an attractant to *B. zonata* and MFF. Hemeida *et al.* (2017) reported that when added di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (3%) to the commercially protein-based baits of Buminal (5%) with a ratio of 1:1 significantly increased its efficiency as attractants for *B. zonata* adults from 3.4 to 6.8 times.

The attractants affected the sexes similarly in terms of relative responses (Yee, 2007). Epsky *et al.* (2014) and Piñero *et al.* (2015) explained the importance of proteins for fruit flies females to complete egg maturation; so, this indicated the main cause for the strong attraction of females to the protein-based baits. These may support the present results which showed that all concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate tended to catch MFF females more than males. A similar conclusion was obtained by Yee (2007), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017), Ghanim (2018) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021); they reported that various ammonium

compounds attracted higher numbers of females of fruit flies than males. Piñero *et al.* (2015) explained that adding ammonium compounds to a variety of protein baits and materials enhanced a response of MFF females more than males.

On the contrary, the present results revealed that the efficiency of all concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate increased as attractants for MFF adults by the passed time over 15 days of the experiment. Also, the results of Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021) came in the trend of the present one. However, they noted that the efficiency of ammonium compounds in attracting fruit flies increased as time passed. On the other hand, Ghanim *et al.* (2014) reported that the efficiency of ammonium acetate was less effective for the tephritid, *Carpomya incompleta* (Becker) (Diptera: Tephritidae) decreased by the passed time in Saudi Arabia. The difference between these results and the present may be attributed to the variation of fruit fly species and/or climatic factors.

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Evaluation of some microbial compounds against land snail species under field conditions at
Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate

Nadia, M. Mostafa; Fatma, K. Khidr and Abou-Hashem, A.A.M.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

This study was conducted at Abu-Abdalla village, Sedy Salem district, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during two successive seasons 2021/2022. To evaluate the bactericidal activity of protecto and the fungicidal activity of biofly on population density reduction of various land snail species infesting Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) as a field crop and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) trees as orchard crop, using rates (500, 250 and 125 gm /200 L.W./Fadden and (100, 75 and 50 cm/100L.W /Fadden), respectively using spray methods. Same tested compound (Protecto and Biofly) at the same rates and method of application were used against *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and *Theba pisana* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snails infesting orange (*Citrus sinensis*) trees at the same location. In addition, Protecto and Biofly were tested as poison bait in concentrations of 5, 10 and 15 % against *M. cantiana* and *T. pisana* infesting orange trees. The tested compound reduced *M. cantiana* population at the different concentrations with variable degrees. The reduction of the population started with low values after the second day of treatment, but the reduction increased gradually to reach its maximum at the end of tested period (15 days).

Introduction

In Egypt, the destructiveness of land snails is far greater today than in former time (Kassab and Daoud, 1964; El-Okda, 1983 and Abdallah *et al.*, 1992). Land snails have been concentrated in the northern Governorate of Delta region and in Upper Egypt to several host plants. These animals become active all year and their activities increase in spring and autumn seasons

(Godan, 1983). These snails become an important agricultural pest, causing great damage to different crops and orchards production in different localities.

These snails were recorded with relatively high population density on major economic crops at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate (Sharsher *et al.*, 1996). Until now, these pests are controlled chemically by synthetic molluscicides or insecticides

(Crowell, 1967 and El-Okda,1981). These chemical compounds cause environmental contamination which gives rise to residues in food, fruits, and water.

Therefore, it was necessary to apply some methods as a biological control to the management of the snails population under field conditions by using microbial compounds (Abdel Megeed et al., 1998; Zedan et al.1999; Sleem, 2002; Idrees, 2003; Gaber et al., 2005; Khider et al ., 2006 and Mortada et al., 2009) .

Materials and methods

Effect of two microbial compounds on various land snail species infesting different crops:

1. Tested microbial compounds:

-Protecto

Bacillus thuringiensis var Kurstaki active ingredient 9.4% and inert ingredient 90.6%.

- Biofly

Beauveria bassiana 30 x 10³ conidia / cm.

2. To evaluate the bactericidal activity of protecto and the fungicidal activity of biofly on population density reduction of various land snail species infesting Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) as a field crop and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) trees as orchard crop, field experimental was carried out at Abu- Abdalla village, Sedy Salem district, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during successive season 2021 /2022. For these studies two experiments areas (One feddan each) were chosen, the first area was cultivated with Egyptian clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) which high infested with *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and *Succinea putris* (L.) (Pulmonata: Succineidae) snails . These snails were found in clover plantations in high density compared with other snail species. The second area was cultivated with citrus trees, orange (*C. sinensis*) which were infested with *M. cantiana* and *Theba*

pisana (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snails. The tested biocides were applied at rats (125, 250 and 500 gm /200 L.W/Feddan) for Protecto and (50, 70 and 100 ml/100 L.W/Feddan) for Biofly, spraying method was used. . The experiments were conducted in a completely randomized block design consisting of two treatments including control and replicated five times (5x5m each). The remaining experimental area acted as a buffer between plots. The tested compounds were sprayed after three days of irrigation on the damp soil in the evening. In the case of orange trees, five trees infested with *M.cantiana* and *T. pisana* snails for each treatment and snails population on trees trunks (One meter) and on soil surrounded trees (One meter diameter) were counted . Protecto and Biofly were used as poison baits, the rate of 2 ,3, 5 and 10 gm % for Protecto and 2 ,3, 5, and 10 cm% for Biofly. Toxic bran baits used against snails infested orange trees, placed plastic sheets around trees (El- Okda , 1983). The snails population (Snails / 0.5 m²) was recorded before and after 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 12 and 15 days post treatment. Reduction percentages were calculated according to **Henderson and Tilton equation (1955):**

$$R \% = (1 - t_2 \times r_1 / t_1 \times r_2) \times 100$$

Whereas:

t = Population size at treated area

r = Population size at untreated area

t₁ x r₁ = Pre-treatment

t₂ x r₂ =post-treatment

Results and discussion

Effect of certain microbial compounds against some land snails infesting different crops under field conditions:

The efficacy of Protecto and Biofly was evaluated against *M. cantiana* and *S.putris* infesting Egyptian clover (*T. alexandrinum*) at Abu- Abdalla village, using rates (500 ,250 and 125 gm /200 L.W./Fadden and (100, 75 and 50 cm/100L.W /Fadden), respectively using spray methods. The same tested

compound at the same rates and method of application was used against *M. cantiana* and *T. pisana* snails infesting orange (*C. sinensis*) trees at the same location. In addition to, Protecto and Biofly were tested as poison baits in concentrations of 5, 10 and 15 % against *M.cantiana* and *T.pisana* infesting orange trees . The tested compound reduced *M. cantiana* population at the different concentrations with variable degrees. The reduction of the population started with low values after the second day of treatment, but the reduction increased gradually to reach its maximum at the end of the tested period (15 days).

Table (1) : Effect of various microbial compounds against *Monacha cantiana* snails clover using spray method under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compounds	Tested rates	% Reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protecto	500 mg	0	32.1	49.6	60.1	79.3	84.5	89.6	93.5	61.0
	250	0	19.6	28.5	47.5	61.2	70.5	76.2	80.1	48.0
	125	0	0	16.1	38.2	63.0	66.1	69.3	71.5	40.5
Biofly	500 cm	0	19.1	33.6	57.5	60.0	64.1	70.2	83.1	48.5
	250	0	17.2	19.0	36.2	47.2	53.0	68.1	69.5	38.8
	125	0	0	13.0	21.5	29.0	33.6	49.5	61.3	26.0

Data in Table (2) showed that, Protecto at rates 500, 250 and 125 gm / 200L.W/ Feddan reduced *S. putris* population snails at 2nd and 15th days post treatment with (41.6 and 83.1%), (20.4 and 73.0 %) and (16.1 and 51.2 %) , respectively. The average reduction % for the tested rates after 15 days post treatment

Table (2) : Effect of some microbial compounds against *Succenia putris* snails on clover using a spray method under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compound	Tested rates	%Reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protecto	500 mg	0	41.6	39.0	46.3	60.9	68.2	76.3	83.1	52.3
	250	0	20.4	31.0	43.5	55.1	64.2	69.2	73.0	44.6
	125	0	16.1	19.7	31.7	42.2	44.1	47.1	51.2	32.5
Biofly	100 cm	0	23.1	43.7	64.7	67.2	74.0	78.1	80.0	53.9
	75	0	17.6	41.0	58.5	67.7	72.0	71.0	72.0	50
	50	0	15.2	27.4	49.0	54.9	60.7	70.3	61.5	42.4

Data in Table (3) showed that , applied Protecto at rates 500 , 250 and 125 gm/200 L.W/Feddan to reduced population snails *M.chantiana* on orange trees at 2nd

Data in Table (1) showed t respectively ,t rates 500 , 250 and 125 gm /200L.W/Feddan reduced *M. cantiana* population on clover at the 2nd and 15th day post treatment with (32.1 and 93%) , (19.6 and 80.1 %) and (16.1 and 71,6 %), respectively The average rate of reduction for the three tested rates after 15 days post treatment were 61.0 , 45.0 and 40.5 % , while Biofly at rates of 100 , 75 and 50 cm /100 L.W/Feddan exhibited (19.1 and 83.1%) , (17.2 and 69.5 %) and (13.2 and 61.3 %) reduction at 2nd and 15th days post treatment respectively, with average % reduction of 48.5, 38.8 and 26.0 %.

was 52, 3, 44.6 and 31.5 % , respectively. On the other hand, Biofly at rates 100, 75 and 50 cm /100L.W/Feddan exhibited (23.1 and 80.0%), (17.6 and 72.0 %) and (15.2 and 61.5%) reductions at 2nd and 15th post treatment, respectively with average % reduction of 53.9, 50.0 and 42.4% at the same tested period and concentration.

and 15th days post treatment with (21.6 and 74.1%) , (26.0 and 64.7%)and (0 and 60.6%) , respectively .The average % reduction for the three tested concentrations

after 15 days post treatment were 42.9 , 38.3 and 30.5 % , respectively while Biofly at rates 100 ,75 and 50 cm / 100 L.W/ Feddan of orange trees were (18.6 and

59.6%) , (23.4 and 46.3%) and (0 and 30.4%) reduction at 2nd and 15th post treatment ,respectively with average reduction% of 32.7 , 31.4 and 17.6% .

Table (3): Effect of two microbial compounds against *Monacha cantiana* snails on orange as spray method under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compound	Tested rates	% reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protcto	500 mg	0	21.6	34.3	39.3	46.1	59.3	68.2	74.1	42.9
	250	0	26.0	31.0	33,6	49.1	50.6	51.1	64.7	38.3
	125	0	0	20.3	35.1	38.2	40.4	49.2	60.5	30.5
Biofly	100 cm	0	18.6	24.3	22.7	36.0	49.2	51.3	59.6	32.7
	75	0	23.4	29.4	26.3	30.0	48.4	45.2	46.3	31.4
	50	0	0	18.7	20.0	20.1	23.2	28.1	30.4	17.6

Data in Table (4) showed that application of Protecto at the same rates reduced *T.pisana* snails population at 2nd and 15th days post treatment with (39.2 and 81.3%) , (27.1 and 69.4%) and 18.3 and 59.7 %)respectively with average %reduction 50.3 , 41.4 and 33.2% , while Biofly at the same

rates on orange trees exhibited (24.1 and 70.3%) , (16.3 and 64.1%) and (0 and 51.5%) .The following results showed that effect of various bio-compounds as poison baits against *M.chantiana* and *T.pisana* snails infesting orange trees at the same location during Spring season of 2022.

Table (4): Effect of two microbial compounds against *Theba pisana* snails on orange trees as a spray method under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compounds	Tested rates	%Reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protecto	500 mg	0	39.2	43.5	50.1	50.0	62.1	76.1	81.3	50.3
	250	0	27.1	30.2	39.4	46.8	57.2	61.3	69.4	41.4
	125	0	18.3	29.1	31.1	30.2	46.1	51.3	59.7	33.2
Biofly	100 cm	0	24.1	39.3	48.0	59.0	68.0	70.1	70.3	47.4
	75	0	16.3	39.34.6	33,5	39.0	47.1	64.1	64.1	41.4
	50	0	0	11.0	29.1	40.3	42.0	51.5	51.5	28.0

Data in Table (5) showed that, the biocid Protecto at rates 15, 10 and 5 gm % reduced *M. chantiana* snails population at 2nd and 15th days post treatment with (21.6 and 81.3%), (14.0 and 69.7%) and (0 and 48.1%) , respectively . The average % reduction for

the three rates after 15 days post treatment was 41.4, 30.7 and 25.2%, respectively. Biofly exhibited (11.2 and 64.1%), (0 and 60%) and (0 and 28.1%) with average 29 .9 ,27.8 and 15.3%, respectively at the same tested period and concentration.

Table (5): Effect of two microbial compounds against *Monacha cantiana* snails on orange trees as a poison bait under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compounds	Tested rates	%Reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protecto	15 gm	0	21.6	29.3	33.2	41.6	58.1	66.1	81.3	41.4
	10	0	14.0	21.2	24.0	29.6	36.1	51.2	69.7	30.7
	5	0	0	16.1	30.0	30.6	33.1	40.6	48.1	25.2
Biofly	15	0	11.2	19.3	22.0	27.6	42.7	51.9	64.1	29.9
	10	0	0	16.3	24.3	33.4	39.6	48.7	60.0	27.8
	5	0	0	12.0	18.0	20.0	20.3	24.0	28.1	15.3

Data in Table (6) showed that, Protecto at rates 15, 10 and 5 gm % reduced *T. pisana* snails population at 2nd and 15th days post treatment with (31.6 and 70.2%) ,(19.6 and 61.3%) and (0 and 49.0%), respectively with average 41.6 , 37.2 and

27.0% , respectively at the same tested period and concentrations. Also, Biofly exhibited (10.1 and 60.0%) , (0 and 49,0%) and (0 and 40%) with average % reduction 25.3 , 22,5 and 20.5% respectively.

Table (6): Effect of two microbial compounds against *Theba pisana* snails on orange trees as a poison bait under field conditions during spring season 2022.

Tested compounds	Tested rates	% Reduction after days								Mean
		1	2	3	5	7	9	12	15	
Protecto	15 gm	0	31.6	39.2	36.8	48.1	49.0	58.0	70.2	41.6
	10	0	19.6	30.1	38.5	38.0	53.1	57.1	61.3	37.2
	5	0	0	16.3	28.4	41.6	37.5	42.6	49.0	27.0
Biofly	15	0	10.1	19.3	18.3	24.0	29/0	41.9	60.0	25.3
	10	0	0	14.6	21.6	26.0	28.0	40.5	49.0	22.5
	5	0	0	9.0	15.1	24.6	39.1	36.3	40.0	20.5

These results agree with those, Lokma and Al-Harby (1999) tested Protecto 9.4% containing *B. thuringiensis* as a biocid under laboratory and field conditions against the snails *Monacha cartusiana* (Muller) (Gastropoda:Helicoidea) and *Rumina decollate* (L.) (Gastropoda: Subulinidae). The results revealed that Protecto as a soking spray was more effective than baits against the two snails under laboratory conditions. Soking spray method gave high mortality percentage, reaching 100% for *M. cartusiana* when used at concentration of 10 gm of protecto 9.4% / 100 ml water, while mortality percentage did not exceed 56% for *R. decollate*. At the same time, toxic baits application used at 10 gm of Protecto 9.4% /100gm bran gave 90% mortality against *M. cartusiana* and 52% against *R. decollate*. The field experimental trial indicated that mortality was caused by using Protecto 9.4%at 10 gm /100 ml water concentration as soking spray against *Monacha* sp. Was 80%. The obtained results encourage more studies for estimating the potential of biocides against land snails. Sleem (2002) studied that ,the effect of vertemic on the digestive gland of the land snails *E. vermiculata* , he found that a low sublethal dose of vertemic (0.05 mg of Abamactine /snail / day) induced tubule cells

vaculation of digestive gland and on increase in the yellowish spherules , while higher sublethal dose of vertemic (0.15 mgob Abamactin /snail/day) caused sever general damage in the digestive tubules , tubular epithelial degeneration and marked loss of the entire digestive gland structure , widening of tubular and complete necrosis.

Idrees (2003) tested both *B. thuringiensis* var *Barlliner* and *B. thuringiensis* var *Karstaki* in addition to *B. bassiana* 3×10^6 conidia /cm for biological control of the three land snails, *M. cantiana*, *T. pisana* and *S. putris*. results revealed that *B. bassiana* 3×10^6 (Biofly) was the highest toxic action against *M. cantiana* followed by *B. thuringiensis* var *Berliner* and *B. thorengensis* var *kurstaki* when using as a leaf dipping technique. Results of poison baits treatments of *B. thorengensis* var *Berliner* against various land snail species revealed that, *T. pisana* was the most sensitive to tested compounds (LC₅₀ 2.69 ppm) followed by *M. cantiana* (LC₅₀ 3.9 ppm), while *S. putris* snails were LC₅₀ 5.8.

In conclusion, control responsibility and / or the farmer must be taken into account, two important factors, where and when mollusciciding operations were carried out during the course of the present study. It is interesting to notice that terrestrial snails

were active only after irrigation, in moist weather, in damp evenings and early morning hours. It is thus under these circumstances that snails can come into contact with molluscicides. Also, the density of snails population are increases at field edges, especially beside field water canals, in tall herbs and under weeds which cover pontes, therefore, focal/ seasonal mollusciciding operations are likely to be the role rather than blanket (=area wide). Also, the present study indicated biological control plays an important role in reducing the population numbers of snail infestation minimize environmental pollution.

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Population density of leafminer *Liriomyza trifolii* (Diptera: Agromyzidae) on early tomato season as influenced by seed treatments and spraying plants

El-Fakharany, S. K. M. and Samy, M. A.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

Liriomyza trifolii (Burgess) (Diptera: Agromyzidae) is one of the most important pests in which host range causing serious losses in several economically important crops. Thus, greenhouse and field experiments were conducted at Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate in the two plantations (March and July), season 2022 to study the population density of *L. trifolii* on tomatoes as affected by tomato varietal preference and to determine, efficiency to certain compounds through tomato seed treatments and spraying plants. The number of leafminer larvae appeared in the first week of May in Angham, Thurayia and Elissa cultivars tomato in plantations, and then it increased gradually to reach the highest peak in the second week of May. Also, it started at low density in the second week of August in July plantation and the highest peak of pest was recorded in the fourth week of August in the three cultivars. The population densities of *L. trifolii* larvae were higher on Elissa cultivar than on Angham and Thurayia in April and July plantations. Thus, it should differ significantly between Elissa C.V. and Angham ($p \leq 0.05$). This pest was lower in the first plantation than in the second one. Difenconazole 2.2%+ fludioxonil 2.2% + thiamethoxam 22.6% (I) and fludioxonil 2% +thiamethoxam 20% (II) compounds induced a fast initial effect where the reduction in population was 100% on all varieties in the two plantations, while the effect decreased gradually to reach zero% reduction after 5 weeks. Significant differences were found among treatments and control on the mean number of *L. trifolii* larvae on all cultivars ($p \leq 0.05$). The general mean of reduction in insect population throughout the scouting period, (I) and (II) compounds significantly induced the highest reduction in the two plantations. Thus, it did not differ significantly in the two compounds with cultivars as tomato seed treatments against leafminer ($p \geq 0.05$). Cyromazine and abamectin were the most potent compounds in reducing the population density of leafminer in tomato plants in the two plantations. It was followed by thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, while fipronil was the least in this pest control.

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L.) is important vegetable crop grown in Egypt. There is a number of insect pests attacking tomato crop from the emergence of seeds to fruit harvesting. Tomato leafminer is one of the main insect pests of tomatoes in different tomato-growing countries. Almost twenty-four different host plants were identified infested by leafminers i.e., *Liriomyza* spp. on tomato (89% infestation) (Hamza *et al.*, 2023).

Worldwide, there are more than 330 leafminer species that belong to genus *Liriomyza* which are important insect pests of many vegetables and ornamental plants (Gao *et al.*, 2017). Leafminer *Liriomyza trifolii* (Burgess) (Diptera: Agromyzidae) in its immature stage lives inside and consumes the leaf tissues of host plants. It is a major insect pest of vegetables and ornamentals, especially tomato crop in the Mediterranean countries and worldwide (Spencer, 1990; Seal *et al.*, 2002 and Hamza *et al.*, 2023). This pest can cause major production and economic losses in host crops also larvae feed on the mesophyll layer of leaves, which reduces the photosynthetic area, leaf chlorophyll content and water losses in the plants (Bueno *et al.*, 2007; Yıldırım *et al.*, 2010 and Thorat *et al.*, 2017).

Regarding the management of agromyzid leafminers, there had been an extensive debate among researchers. Farmers commonly used synthetic and natural insecticides for the control of this pest for better production of vegetables especially tomatoes. Due to the use of these insecticides in a disorganized way, the effectiveness of these insecticides is reduced. These include abamectin, cyromazine, thiocyclam hydrogen oxylate and bensultap insecticides (Weintraub, 2001; Civelek and Weintraub, 2003; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2008; Hernández *et al.*, 2011; Reitz *et al.*, 2013; Morsy *et al.*, 2019; Chang *et al.*, 2022 and Hamza *et al.*, 2023)

significantly reduced *L. trifolii* larvae on plants. To the best of our knowledge, few works have been reported regarding tomato seed treatments, tomato varietal preference of leafminer and efficacy of different insecticides for management strategies.

These findings will provide some basic information and management options to reduce the pest population.

Materials and methods

1. Population density of *Liriomyza trifolii*:

The population for *L. trifolii* infestation tomato (*L. esculentum* L. var. Angham, Thurayia and Elissa.) crop was conducted at the farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, during 2022 season in the two plantations. An area of 400 m² was assigned for each tomato variety. On April 15 (The first plantation) and on July 26 (The second plantation) tomato seedlings were transplanted. The inspection started 15 days after transplanting and continued weekly till six weeks. The experimental area was divided into four plots, each variety was represented by four replicates arranged in a complete randomized block design and ten tomato plants were weekly inspected randomly from every replicate. Thus, 40 tomato plants were sampled for every variety at every sampling date.

2. The tested compounds:

The study was carried out to evaluate six compounds; two were applied as seed treatment and the field performance of four insecticides in their respective commercial formulations available on the market. Difenoconazole 2.2%+ fludioxonil 2.2% + thiamethoxam 22.6% (I) (Corner Plus 27% FS), fludioxonil 2% +thiamethoxam 20% (II) (Assure Extra 22% FS, Starchem Industrial Chemicals, Egypt) for seeds treatment; abamectin (Vapcomic1.8% EC, Vapco), thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (Evisects 50% SP, Nippon Kayaku; Arysta), cyromazine

(Cymax 50% SP, Shandong, Sino- Agri United Biotechnology Co., Ltd) and fipronil (Ekiw Safe 50% FS, BASF), for plant treatments. The pesticide generic and chemical information is given in Table (1).

The concentrations used were based on the recommendations of the Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture for each pesticide to control sucking pest insects and leafminers under field conditions.

Table (1): Common and trade names of tested compounds, their chemical classes and application.

Common name	Trade name	Chemical classes	Application rate /Kg
Seeds treatment			
Difenoconazole 2.2%+ fludioxonil 2.2% + thiamethoxam 22.6% (I)	Corner Plus 27% FS	Triazole+phenylpyrrole neonicotinoid	4 ml
Fludioxonil 2% +thiamethoxam 20% (II)	Assure Extra 22% FS	Phenylpyrrole +neonicotinoid	3 ml
Plants treatment			
Abamectin	Vapcomic1.8% EC	Avermectin	40 ml
Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate	Evisects 50% SP	Nereistoxin analogue	250 g
Cyromazine	Cymax 50% SP	Cyromazine	20 g
Fipronil	Ekiw Safe 50% FS	Phenylpyrazole	15 g

3. Seed treatments:

The study was conducted on tomato seeds to evaluate the effect of different treatments against *L. trifolii*. Tomato seeds varieties: Angham, Thurayia and Elissa were spread on clean plastic sheets moistened, then mixed thoroughly with the tested compounds (I) and (II) as shown in Table (1). The treated seeds and control were left to dry, then directly planted in the trays in greenhouse. The planting was carried out in the last week of March (in the first plantation) and the first week of July (in the second plantation) in trays greenhouse (3 trays each variety) in 2022 season. The inspection started 15 days after planting (The appearance of two true leaves) and continued for two weeks, then tomato plants were transplanted in the last week of April (In the first plantation) and the first week of August (In the second plantation) in the open field. The experimental area was divided into four plots, each variety was represented by four replicates arranged in a completely randomized block design and 25 tomato plants were weekly inspected randomly from every replicate. This area did not receive any insecticidal treatments during

the experimental period extending about 7 weeks after planting. The reduction percentage in leafminer population was calculated according to Abbott's Formula (1925).

4. Field assessments:

Field experiments were conducted during June and August 2022 season at the experimental farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh governorate. An area of 1000 m² planted with tomato (*L. esculentum* L. var. Elissa) was divided into plots 200 m² for each treatment and infested with *L. trifolii*. This area did not receive any insecticidal treatments before the start of the experiment. Four insecticides + control was tested in arranged and complete randomized blocks designed with four replicates. The tested compounds were applied at recommended rates using a motor knapsack sprayer, tap water was used for dilutions. Ten tomato leaves were randomly chosen from each replication to count the leafminer population. The chosen plants were examined before spraying and 3, 5 and 10 days post spray. The mean number of *L. trifolii* per 40 tomato leaves (10 leaves/ replicate) was recorded. The

percentage of infestation reductions in leafminer population among treatments in relation to control was calculated according to Flemings and Ratnataran (1985) equation.

5. Statistical analysis:

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was calculated, and significant differences between the means of these treatments by Duncan's Multiple Rang Test (Duncan, 1955) using the SPSS statistical software package 16.0 (SPSS, 2016).

Results and discussion

1. Population density of *Liriomyza trifolii*:

Population densities of *L. trifolii* larvae on tomato plants at the farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh 2022 season are shown in (Figure 1) the numbers of leafminer larvae appeared in the first week of May in Angham, Thurayia and Elissa cultivars tomato in April plantation, then it increased gradually

to reach the highest peak in the second week of May. Also, in Figure (1) *L. trifolii* larvae were started at low density in the second week of August in July plantation. The population increased gradually, and the highest peak of pest was recorded in the fourth week of August in the three cultivars. The present results are in parallel with Abou-Attia *et al.* (2004) who observed the peak of leafminer larvae on tomatoes in May at Kafr El-Sheikh, while Saradhi and Fatniar (2004) in India, recorded the highest infestation of leafminer in the second and third weeks in February on tomato. Tran *et al.* (2007) found that the abundance of leafminer was high at the beginning of the growing season (Cucumber) in July until late August after which the population decreased until the last season. The mean numbers of mines, larvae, and pupae were highest at 2 weeks on snap beans and 3 weeks on squash after planting (Devkota and Seal, 2021).

Figure (1): Population densities of *Liriomyza trifolii* larvae on tomato plants at Sakha Agricultural Research Station farm in 2022 season.

2. Tomato varietal preference of leafminer:

The population densities of *L. trifolii* larvae were higher on Elissa cultivar (9.67 and 13.63) than on Angham (6.42 and 9.88) and Thurayia (8.88 and 12.83) in April and July plantations respectively. Thus, it should differ significantly between Elissa c.v. and Angham ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 2). Leafminer larvae were lower in the first plantation than in the second one. The mine numbers in each tomato leaflet varied from 1 to 9, but the leaflets with 2 mines were the most frequent case (Lee *et al.*, 2004). Also, Lee *et al.*

(2005) found that the mean number of leafmines per leaf ranged from 1.02 to 11.04 in the first season, while it was from 0.16 to 9.97 in the second. Lalruatsangi and Chatterjee (2022) found that the highest leafminer infestation was recorded on cultivar Mahy Gotya, while it least was recorded on cultivar MT-2 and Selection-1. Hamza *et al.* (2023) showed that Baby red variety of tomato crop was the most preferred by leafminer (*Liriomyza* spp.), and comparatively Sehar was the least preferred variety.

Table (2): Tomato varietal preference of leafminer in 2022 season at Sakha Agricultural Research Station farm, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

Plantation	Seasonal mean of <i>Liriomyza trifolii</i> larvae /10 tomato plants \pm SE		
	Angham	Thurayia	Elissa
April	6.42 ^b \pm 0.71	8.88 ^{ab} \pm 1.08	9.67 ^a \pm 1.08
July	9.88 ^b \pm 0.82	12.83 ^{ab} \pm 1.22	13.63 ^a \pm 1.22

In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan (1955)

3. Seed treatments:

The data presented in Table (3) showed the mean number of *L. trifolii* larvae on tomato plants and reduction percentage as influenced by (I) and (II) compounds applied as tomato seed treatments on three tomato

cultivars (At recommended) in the two plantations, 2022 season. It was apparent that (I) and (II) compounds induced a fast initial effect where the reduction in population was 100% on all varieties; Angham, Thurayia and Elissa in the two plantations, while the effect

decreased gradually to reach zero% reduction after 5 weeks. Significant differences were found among treatments and control on a

mean number of *L. trifolii* larvae on all cultivars ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table (3): Mean number and percentage reduction of *Liriomyza trifolii* larvae on tomato plants in different periods from appearance two true leaves in 2022 season.

Compound	Variety	Average No. of leafminer/25 tomato plants \pm SE and reduction % after indicated weeks					Grand average reduction%
		In trays ()		In field			
		One	2	3	4	5	
March plantation							
(I)	Angham	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.25 ^b \pm 0.48	1.0 ^b \pm 0.41	2.0 ^b \pm 0.41	13.0 ^a \pm 1.08	
		(100)	(90)	(71.43)	(46.67)	(0.0)	61.62
(II)	Angham	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.5 ^b \pm 0.29	1.5 ^b \pm 0.29	2.5 ^{ab} \pm 0.29	16.0 ^a \pm 1.08	
		(100)	(80.0)	(64.29)	(33.33)	(0.0)	55.53
Untreated		1.0 ^a \pm 0.41	2.5 ^a \pm 0.29	3.5 ^a \pm 0.29	3.75 ^a \pm 0.48	13.0 ^a \pm 1.08	-
(I)	Thurayia	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.5 ^b \pm 0.29	1.25 ^b \pm 0.48	2.75 ^b \pm 0.25	16.0 ^a \pm 1.08	
		(100)	(86.67)	(68.75)	(38.89)	(0.0)	58.86
(II)	Thurayia	0.0 ^b \pm 0	1.0 ^b \pm 0.41	1.5 ^b \pm 0.29	3.0 ^b \pm 0.41	17.0 ^a \pm 2.16	
		(100)	(73.33)	(62.5)	(33.33)	(0.0)	53.83
Untreated		1.0 ^a \pm 0.41	3.75 ^a \pm 0.48	4.0 ^a \pm 0.41	4.5 ^a \pm 0.65	16.0 ^a \pm 1.08	-
(I)	Elissa	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.5 ^b \pm 0.29	1.25 ^b \pm 0.25	3.0 ^b \pm 0.41	18.0 ^a \pm 1.47	
		(100)	(87.5)	(68.75)	(36.84)	(0.0)	58.62
(II)	Elissa	0.0 ^b \pm 0	1.0 ^b \pm 0.41	1.75 ^b \pm 0.25	3.25 ^b \pm 0.25	19.0 ^a \pm 1.08	
		(100)	(75.0)	(56.25)	(31.58)	(0.0)	52.57
Untreated		1.25 ^a \pm 0.41	4.0 ^a \pm 0.41	4.0 ^a \pm 0.41	4.75 ^a \pm 0.48	18.0 ^a \pm 1.47	-
July plantation							
(I)	Angham	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.5 ^b \pm 0.14	1.5 ^b \pm 0.29	2.75 ^b \pm 0.14	9.0 ^a \pm 1.15	
		(100)	(83.33)	(73.91)	(54.17)	(0.0)	62.28
(II)	Angham	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.75 ^b \pm 0.14	1.75 ^b \pm 0.14	3.0 ^b \pm 0.58	10.25 ^a \pm 0.58	
		(100)	(75.0)	(69.57)	(50.0)	(0.0)	58.91
Untreated		1.25 ^a \pm 0.14	3.0 ^a \pm 0.58	5.75 ^a \pm 0.58	6.0 ^a \pm 0.58	9.0 ^a \pm 1.15	-
(I)	Thurayia	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.75 ^b \pm 0.14	2.0 ^b \pm 0.29	4.0 ^b \pm 0.58	11.25 ^a \pm 0.58	
		(100)	(81.25)	(71.43)	(46.67)	(0.0)	59.87
(II)	Thurayia	0.0 ^b \pm 0	1.0 ^b \pm 0.14	2.5 ^b \pm 0.29	4.25 ^b \pm 0.58	11.5 ^a \pm 1.15	
		(100)	(75.0)	(64.29)	(43.33)	(0.0)	56.52
Untreated		1.5 ^a \pm 0.29	4.0 ^a \pm 0.58	7.0 ^a \pm 0.58	7.5 ^a \pm 0.87	11.0 ^a \pm 1.15	-
(I)	Elissa	0.0 ^b \pm 0	0.75 ^b \pm 0.14	2.75 ^b \pm 0.29	4.25 ^b \pm 0.58	13.5 ^a \pm 0.58	
		(100)	(82.35)	(65.63)	(48.48)	(0.0)	59.29
(II)	Elissa	0.0 ^b \pm 0	1.0 ^b \pm 0.14	3.0 ^b \pm 0.58	4.5 ^b \pm 0.58	14.0 ^a \pm 1.15	
		(100)	(76.47)	(62.5)	(45.45)	(0.0)	56.88
Untreated		1.5 ^a \pm 0.29	4.25 ^a \pm 0.43	8.0 ^a \pm 0.58	8.25 ^a \pm 0.58	13.0 ^a \pm 1.15	-

In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan (1955).

Based on the general mean of reduction in insect population throughout the scouting period, (I) and (II) compounds significantly induced the highest reduction 62.28 to 52.57% in the two plantations. Thus,

it did not differ significantly in the two compounds with cultivars as tomato seed treatments against leafminer ($p \geq 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table (4): General means of reduction of *Liriomyza trifolii* larvae as tomato seed treatments.

Compound	Grand average reduction% \pm SE		
	Angham	Thurayia	Elissa
March plantation			
(I)	61.62 ^a \pm 3.46	58.86 ^a \pm 2.89	58.62 ^a \pm 3.46
(II)	55.53 ^a \pm 2.31	53.83 ^a \pm 2.89	52.57 ^a \pm 1.73
July plantation			
(I)	62.28 ^a \pm 3.46	59.87 ^a \pm 4.04	59.29 ^a \pm 2.31
(II)	58.91 ^a \pm 3.46	56.52 ^a \pm 2.89	56.88 ^a \pm 2.31

In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan (1955).

Hamid *et al.* (2003), El-Dewy (2006) and El-Naggar (2006) revealed that imidacloprid and thiamethoxam as seed treatment had relatively fast initial effects against thrips on cotton and the residual efficiency lasted for 7 weeks after planting.

The insecticide efficacy of four compounds, from different chemical groups presented in Table (5) was evaluated under field conditions for their efficacy against *L. trifolii* infesting tomato plants at Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during two plantations, 2022 season. It is obvious that cyromazine (91.94 and 91.89%) and abamectin (89.43 and 89.94%) were the most potent compounds in reducing the population density of leafminer in tomato plants in the two plantations. It was followed by thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, while fipronil was the least in this pest control. Significant differences were found among treatments (Cyromazine, abamectin and thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate) and fipronil in reduction of *L. trifolii* larvae ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 5).

Results were in accordance with that reported by Weintraub (1999 and 2001) who found that abamectin and cyromazine

significantly reduced leafminer as compared to non-treated control; however, cyromazine was significantly more effective than abamectin. Civelek and Weintraub (2003) also mentioned cyromazine and bensultap significantly reduced *L. trifolii* larvae on tomato plants as compared to non-treated control; however, bensultap at 3.0 kg/ha was significantly more effective than at 2.5 kg/ha. Ibrahim *et al.* (2008) found that profenofos was the most potent chemical used against *L. trifolii*, while thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate was the lowest effective in this pest. Hernández *et al.* (2011) found the plants pepper treated with abamectin had lower leafminer density than those in the untreated control. Morsy *et al.* (2019) found the highest reduction in *L. trifolii* population occurred with cyromazine followed by abamectin, while it was low by bemistop. Chang *et al.* (2022) found that the genes related to *L. trifolii* hormones were significantly expressed after treatment with cyromazine. Hamza *et al.* (2023) found that the highest reduction was observed for spinetoram, whereas bifenthrin. Deltaphos was the least toxic insecticide against *Liriomyza* spp.

Table (5): Potency of tested compounds in reducing *Liriomyza trifolii* larvae on tomato plants in 2022 season at Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

Compound	Used* conc. [mg a.i.l ⁻¹]	Aver. No. pre-treat. /10 leaves	% Reduction				
			Initial effect % (3)	Residual effect after indicated days		Residual effect average	Grand Average
				5	10		
March plantation							
Abamectin	7.20	7.25	83.48 ^a ±2.89	89.77 ^a ±2.31	95.04 ^a ±1.73	92.41 ^a ±2.31	89.43 ^a ±2.31
Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate	1250	9.75	68.06 ^b ±1.73	88.5 ^a ±2.89	94.95 ^a ±1.73	91.73 ^a ±1.73	83.84 ^a ±3.46
Cyromazine	100	5.25	86.31 ^a ±2.31	92.93 ^a ±1.73	96.58 ^a ±1.15	94.76 ^a ±2.31	91.94 ^a ±2.31
Fipronil	75	10.5	45.24 ^c ±2.89	71.74 ^b ±2.31	82.89 ^b ±2.31	77.32 ^b ±2.89	66.62 ^b ±1.73
Control (No.)	-	5.75	6.0	7.75	8.0	-	-
July plantation							
Abamectin	7.20	8.75	79.22 ^{ab} ±2.31	92.86 ^a ±2.89	97.74 ^a ±1.15	95.30 ^a ±2.31	89.94 ^a ±2.89
Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate	1250	8.25	72.45 ^b ±2.89	89.89 ^a ±2.89	95.22 ^a ±2.31	92.56 ^a ±2.31	85.85 ^a ±2.31
Cyromazine	100	10.0	81.82 ^a ±2.31	95.83 ^a ±1.73	98.03 ^a ±0.58	96.93 ^a ±1.73	91.89 ^a ±2.89
Fipronil	75	9.0	54.55 ^c ±2.31	74.54 ^b ±2.31	84.65 ^b ±2.89	79.60 ^b ±4.61	71.25 ^b ±2.89
Control (No.)	-	7.5	8.25	9.0	9.5	-	-

* The used concentrations were determined based on the recommendations of Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan (1955).

Almost the mean numbers of larvae were highest at 2 to 3 weeks on tomato after planting. Difenoconazole 2.2%+ fludioxonil 2.2% + thiamethoxam 22.6% (I) and fludioxonil 2% +thiamethoxam 20% (II) as seed treatment had relatively initial effects against leafminer on tomato and the residual efficiency lasted for 5weeks after planting. Tomato varieties tested almost all were found susceptible to leafminer attack, however Angham, a variety of tomatoes showed relatively less attack than other varieties i.e., Thurayia and Elissa. Cyromazine and abamectin proved to be more effective against *L. trifolii* than other insecticides tested.

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Biochemical impacts and toxicity of Bis-(1,2-diphenyl-2-(p-tolylimino)-ethanone and its metal complexes against *Monacha obstructa* and *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae: Helicidae)

Esam, M. Emar

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

The toxic effects of the Schiff base ligand (L); bis-(1,2-diphenyl-2-(p-tolylimino) ethanone and its Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) chloro complexes along with diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA) were screened against *Monacha obstructa* (Pfeiffer) (Gastropoda :Hygromiidae) and *Eobania vermiculata* Müller (Gastropoda: Helicidae) under laboratory conditions. A thin layer film technique was employed to assess the median lethal concentration for the investigated compounds. Five concentrations of the screened compounds were prepared using distilled water and DMSO. The obtained results emphasized that *E. vermiculata* was comparatively less susceptible to the Schiff base ligand, MDA and complexes (1-3) than *M. obstructa*. There were different sensitivity levels between the two tested snail species according to the type of tested compounds. The biochemical impact of the Schiff base ligand and its Cu (II) complex on the activity of alanine amino transaminase (ALT), aspartate amino transaminase (AST) and total proteins (TP) of *E. vermiculata* was reported. The data demonstrated that treatment with the ligand decreased the activities of ALT, AST and TP with mean values (4.67 ± 0.42), (67 ± 3.86) and (0.98 ± 0.14) less than control, respectively, whereas, ALT, AST activities and TP were increased after treated with complex (3) with mean values (7.44 ± 0.31), (16.34 ± 1.06) and (0.51 ± 0.08) more than the control, respectively.

Introduction

Land snails are molluscs, a group of invertebrate animals with soft unsegmented bodies that are enclosed in calcareous shells (Barker, 2001; Larramendy and Soloneski, 2012 and South, 1992).

Two common land snails, *Monacha obstructa* (Pfeiffer) (Gastropoda :Hygromiidae) and *Eobania vermiculata* Müller (Gastropoda: Helicidae) are

important crop pests that cause considerable damage in agriculture, especially in areas where they find the conditions necessary for rapid multiplication. Damage caused by snails depends not only on their activity and population density, but also on their feeding habits, which differ from one species to another. Damage involving considerable financial loss is inflicted on cereal,

vegetables, clover as well as other agricultural and field crops.

The land snails feed on leaves, roots, tubers, and ornamental plants (El-Okda, 1981). In addition, during movement, snails cause an undesirable smell which prevents men and animals from feeding on these contaminated plants (El-Okda, 1984). The chemistry of Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes is very important due to the wide range of applications as antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer and catalytic properties (Dhahagani *et al.*, 2014; Jayabalakrishnan and Karvembu, 2002 and Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2007). In addition, Schiff base complexes have many applications in biological and industrial systems (Uddin *et al.*, 2015). The Schiff base complexes can serve as models for some biomolecules, such as Schiff base nickel (II) complexes which have been

regarded as models for enzymes such as urease (Asadi *et al.*, 2013 and Carlsson *et al.*, 2004).

In the present study, reported on the toxicity and some biochemical effects of the Schiff base ligand and its complexes against *E. vermiculata* and *M. obstructa* under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental:

Benzil and diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA), metal chloride salts, reagents and solvents were of analytical grade (Merck, Sigma and Aldrich) and purchased from commercial suppliers. The Schiff base ligand (L) along with its metal complexes were prepared and identified as reported in the literature (Emam *et al.*, 2017). The chemical structure of the tested compounds is represented in Figure (1).

Figure (1): Structure the Schiff base ligand (L), MDA and its complexes.

3. Laboratory tests:

The thin layer film technique was used to estimate the median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) of the investigated compounds according to Ascher and Mirian (1981) (El Gohary and Genena, 2011 and Mourad, 2014). Five concentrations of the tested compounds were prepared: (50, 150, 250, 350, 450 ppm) using distilled water and DMSO. Two mL of each concentration were deposited and distributed on the bottom of a petri dish by moving the dish gently in circles. Solvents were evaporated under room conditions leaving a thin layer film of the applied concentration of the tested compounds. Five healthy adult snails of the tested species were placed and exposed to the candidate concentration of the tested compound for 72 hrs. A parallel control test was carried out using water and DMSO. Dead snails were counted and removed from the boxes every 24 hrs. Probit analysis was used to compute LC₅₀ values (Finney, 1971). Data were calculated as Mean±SD and analyzed using the Analysis of Variance Technique (ANOVA) followed by Least Significant Differences (LSD). The corrected mortality was calculated according to (Abbott, 1925):

$$\frac{\text{Corrected Mortality}}{100 - \text{Control mortality}} = \frac{\text{Treatment mortality} - \text{Control mortality}}{100 - \text{Control mortality}} * 100$$

4. Biochemical tests on *Eobania vermiculata*:

The experiments were carried out under laboratory conditions 24±1°C and 57±1 RH. The treated snails were transferred from stock culture to plastic cups filled with moist soil and covered with muslin cloth. Biochemical studies were made after three days of treatment. After that, shells of the tested snails were removed by making a cut around the whorls in a continuous manner. Snail tissues were dissected out and all tissues of treatments were homogenized in distilled water and then centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 15 minutes at 5°C in a refrigerated

centrifuge. The supernatants were kept in a freezer till used to determine the activities of alanine amino transaminase (ALT), aspartate amino transaminase (AST) and total proteins (TP). The activities of ALT, AST and TP were determined (Young, 1995 and 2001).

Results and discussion

1. Laboratory experiments:

The obtained data (Table 1) authenticated that *E. vermiculata* and *M. obstructa* species were more susceptible to MDA than the free Schiff base ligand. The toxicity of the free ligand decreases relative to the two land snails upon complexation. The present results showed that *E. vermiculata* was comparatively less susceptible to the Schiff base ligand (L), MDA and complexes (1-3) than *M. obstructa*. Reviewing the above mentioned results, it is obvious that there are different susceptibility levels between the two tested snail species according to the type of tested compound. These differences in the sensitivity levels may be due to the physiological state of the snail which changes from one species to another (Godan, 1983 and El Gohary and Genena, 2011). It is noticeable that MDA has a higher toxicity than the free Schiff base ligand against the two land snail species. This may be attributed to the presence of free amino groups in the former which can react in cells leading to the initiation of carcinogenic process (Garrigós *et al.*, 2002). The relatively high toxicity of the Schiff base ligand is ascribed to the free oxygen and nitrogen atom located in its chemical formula. The three tested metal complexes displayed considerable toxicity against the two land snail species, ascribed to the binding between metal cations and enzymes (El-Samanody *et al.*, 2017a). The results displayed in (Figure 2) demonstrated the relatively high toxicity of copper chelate which was attributed to the high toxic influence of copper cations (El-Samanody *et al.*, 2017b). These cations inactivate ALP

enzyme because of its strong tendency towards free thiol groups (cysteine) in proteins. Moreover, competition occurred by Cu (II) cations for binding with Mg(II) and Zn (II) sites in enzymes, which distort the active centers of these enzymes as a result (El-Samanody *et al.*, 2017b and Alnuaimi *et al.*, 2012). The activity of cobalt ions to ALP and ACP enzymes may be the reason for the high toxicity of the Co (II) chelate (Alnuaimi *et al.*, 2012). Co (II) ions immobilize ALP and ACP enzymes and keep them in an unfavorable conformation. Ni (II) complex has a relatively high cytotoxicity, attributed to its interference with the metabolism of

divalent iron, manganese, calcium, zinc, copper, and magnesium metals, leading to suppression or modification of the toxic effects of Ni (II) cations. It is probable that the toxic impacts of nickel result from its capability to substitute other cations in enzymes and proteins or bind with sulfur, oxygen, and nitrogen atoms of cellular components (enzymes and nucleic acids), which are then inhibited (Cempel and Nickel, 2006). It has been demonstrated that nickel is immunotoxic, affecting the activity of every individual cell type involved in the immunological response (Cempel and Nickel, 2006).

Table (1): LC₅₀ values of MDA, Schiff base ligand (L) and prepared metal complexes against the two land snails.

No.	Compound	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	
		<i>Eobania vermiculata</i>	<i>Monacha obstructa</i>
	L	177.83	144.88
	MDA	62.73	49.58
1	[Co ₃ (L)Cl ₆].0.5EtOH.7.5H ₂ O	432.15	423.12
2	[Ni ₃ (L)Cl ₆].11H ₂ O	444.72	434.16
3	[Cu ₃ (L)Cl ₆].0.5EtOH.5.25H ₂ O	281.83	261.87

Figure (2): LC₅₀ values of the tested compounds against the two land snail species.

2. Biochemical studies:

The results of biochemical tests of the Schiff base ligand (L) and Cu(II) complex (3) on *E. vermiculata* (Figure 3), as model examples, reveal that, treatment with the ligand decreased the activities of ALT, AST and TP with mean values (4.67 ± 0.42), (67 ± 3.86) and (0.98 ± 0.14) less than control, respectively, whereas, ALT, AST activities and TP were increased after treated with complex (3) with mean values (7.44 ± 0.31), (16.34 ± 1.06) and (0.51 ± 0.08) more than control, respectively. These significant changes in AST and ALT activities in *Eobania vermiculata* pointed out the functional disorder of the liver (Choudhary *et al.*, 2003; Kalender *et al.*, 2005; Kammon *et*

al., 2010 and Arfat *et al.*, 2014). However, it is conceivable that the tested compounds might be interacting primarily with the liver and muscle tissue cell membranes. These results in structure damage and changes in enzyme leakage and in metabolism of the constituents. So, tested compounds may pressurize this enzyme into plasma because of enzyme leakage breakdown. It is known that these enzymes are principally localized in the cytoplasm, and they will be secreted into the blood after hepatocellular injury, resulting in an increase in their levels in the serum. Consequently, this study may suggest that any damage in hepatopancreatic cells of land snails may result in alteration in the serum (Hemolymph) AST and ALT levels.

Figure (3): ALT, AST and TP activities of *Eobania vermiculata* after 72 hrs. treatments with the Schiff base ligand (L) and complex (3).

The data presented in this study reveal that the tested chemical compounds caused an alternation in some biochemical targets which could lead to serious metabolic and cellular damage in *E. vermiculata* and *M. obstructa* compared to other chemical traditional pesticides or molluscicides (Mahal *et al.*, 2015). Thus, these compounds may be helpful to control land snails. Further

studies are still needed to provide the most probable mode of action of these compounds on land snails.

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Predation efficacy of *Amblyseius swirskii* (Acari:Phytoseiidae) on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae)

Salwa, M.E. Sholla and Helmy, S. M.Y.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

Development and food consumption of the predatory mite *Amblyseius swirskii* (Athias-Henriot) (Acari:Phytoseiidae) when fed on the first instar nymph of cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) were studied under constant temperature $26^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ RH. The duration of the life cycle of *A. swirskii* was average 9.5 and 6.4 days for females and males, respectively. Females laid 4 eggs during its oviposition period. The duration of life span was 31 and 18 days for females and males, respectively. Total prey consumption was 3.82, 2.83, 2.84, 2.11, 6.14, 3.12, 42.51 and, 2.38 individuals of 1st nymphal stage for larvae, protonymph, deutonymph, adult male and adult female, respectively. The female consumed prey more than male and the male developed faster than the female. The results showed there was a reduction in population of *P. solenopsis*.

Introduction

The cotton mealybugs *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is a highly invasive and harmful pest. It causes a considerable loss of cotton crops in China, India and Pakistan. It was first recorded in Pakistan and India in 2005. It has spread to 43 countries. Insecticidal control is the primary and dominant practice for this pest and its resistance to commonly used insecticides increasing. Biocontrol agents have strong potential for the management of nymphal instar stages (Waqas *et al.*, 2021). *P. solenopsis* infesting maize crop, in Egypt (Abd-El Mageed *et al.*, 2020). It infests mulberry trees (*Morus* spp.) which are cultivated throughout the world (Abdel-

Razzik, 2018). The pest was recorded to colonize 51 plant species belonging to 19 families (Kedar and Saini, 2015). Chandramani *et al.* (2017). *P. solenopsis* was observed as a major insect pest on ashwagandha.

This pest spreads rapidly on different host plants, which infected 29 host plant species belonging to 16 plant families including field crops, vegetables, ornamentals, weeds and fruits (Abdel-Razzik *et al.*, (2015). *P. solenopsis* crinkling, twist and condenses flower, bud, bolls growth and finally it causes yield loss (Sahito *et al.*, 2009). In Egypt, the pest was recorded for the first time infesting *Hibiscus* sp. In September 2009 by Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2010).

The predatory mites are beneficial organisms used to control many different plant pests, including phytophagous mites (Knapp *et al.*, 2018) in vegetable crops (e.g., Tomatoes, sweet peppers, or cucumbers) and ornamental crops (e.g., Roses; Gerson and Weintraub).

Amyloseius swirskii (Athias-Henriot) (Acari:Phytoseiidae) controls several major ornamental and vegetable pests, including white flies (Calvo *et al.*, 2015). Different insect species can be managed by the predaceous mite *A. swirskii* (Riahi *et al.*, 2017).

Phytoseiidae species are by far the most important group of commercially available mite biocontrol agents with about 10 species offered worldwide out of these, *A. swirskii*. Predatory mites, mainly from the family Phytoseiidae play the leading role among the biocontrol agents used (Markus *et al.*, 2018).

In the presence of alternative food or alternative prey, the fecundity of the predator was much higher. *A. swirskii* is a well-known predator that is used for controlling the population of two-spotted spider mites (TSSM), *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: *Tetranychidae*) and green house whitefly (GHWF), *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) Westwood, in strawberry greenhouses. Alternative food sources such as pollen and GHWF. Produced honeydew plays an important role in maintaining the predator population in the absence of pests (Mortazavi *et al.*, 2019).

A. swirskii is an effective biocontrol agent against whitefly and thrips indoors on vegetable crops (Kozlova *et al.*, 2020). *A. swirskii* is a generalist predator that is used to whiteflies, target thrips and pest mites (Etienne *et al.*, 2021). *A. swirskii* is an effective Predatory mite for controlling whiteflies and thrips in protected crops (Paspati *et al.*, 2022).

The object of this study was to determine the efficacy of *A. swirskii* mites on 1st instar nymph of *P. solenopsis* as a biological control agent.

Materials and methods

Experimental design:

1. *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

The first instar nymph of the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* was found and collected from *P. solenopsis* y culture on potato tubers in the laboratory.

2. Maintenance of the mite stock culture:

The predator mite, *A. swirskii* was reared on the two-spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* under laboratory conditions at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (RH.) with 16:8 L:D hrs. Photoperiodic regime.

3. Effect of preys on development:

The rearing arena (3 cm diameter) of castor bean leaves, placed on saturated cotton in glass Petri dishes (9 cm diameter), was used to confine the predator. Water saturated, absorbent cotton strip, 1 cm wide, was placed around the edge of the leaf to prevent mites from escaping and to hold the leaf flat. Thirty *A. swirskii* eggs for each test were transferred individually with affine camel brush to each arena, the newly hatched larvae were supplied with the food resource to be evaluated. Developmental stages were recorded twice daily. Prey 1st nymphal instar of *P. solenopsis* consumed were replaced daily by fresh ones.

4. Effect of preys on longevity and fecundity:

Newly emerged females, after mating, were confined individually in test arenas, along with food to be tested. A few strands of cotton wool were provided as an ovipositor site in each arena. Oviposition and survival were recorded. Thirty females of *A. swirskii* in each experiment were observed daily and each experiment was repeated three times. *A. swirskii* passed through egg, larvae, protonymph and deutonymph stages for both sexes before reaching adulthood as

in other phytoseiid species. Duration of the developmental stages, preoviposition, oviposition, postoviposition periods, longevity, fecundity, lifespan, and food consumption were recorded by using the stereoscopic microscope which was recorded daily.

5. Statistical analysis:

Data were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (F test) and means were compared according to Duncan's Multiple Range test to evaluate the significant differences between the developmental periods and prey consumption of the male and female of the predator *A.swirskii* reared on the 1st nymphal instar of *P. solenopsis*.

Results and discussion

1. Developmental periods of *Amblyseius swirskii* reared on 1stnymphal instar of *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

Both sexes of *A. swirskii* passed through an egg, larvae, protonymph and deutonymph stages before reaching adulthood as in other phytoseiid species. As

shown in Table (1). Egg incubation period of females and males of phytoseiid mite *A.swirskii* was recorded 1.8 days. The duration of the larval stage lasted 2.24 and 1.42 days. The protonymph was 2.44 and 1.83, the deutonymph was 3.42 and 2.22 days. The life cycle duration of *A.swirskii* was average 9.52 and 6.42 days for females and males, respectively. Females laid 19.44 eggs during their oviposition period. The life span recorded 31.21 and 18.34 days for females and males, respectively.

These results are in agreement with El-Sharabasy *et al.* (2017) life span lasted 31.34 days for a female of the predatory mite, *Euseius scutalis* (Athias-Henriot) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) when it fed on eggs of scale insect *Parlatoria ziziphi* (Lucas) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae). While fecundity, longevity and lifespan were lower at 27°C, also feeding capacities were increased with increasing temperature from 22°C to 25°C and then decreased at 27 °C.

Table (1): Mean developmental periods days (±SD) of *Amblyseius swirskii* females and males reared on 1stnymphal instar of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at constant temperature 26 ±2 °C and 70±5 %RH.

Developmental stage	Developmental periods days (Mean ± SD.)	
	Male	Female
Egg	1.81±0.44a	1.82±0.84a
Larva	1.42±0.55b	2.24±0.22a
Protonymph	1.83±0.45b	2.44±0.53a
Deutonymph	2.22±0.63b	3.42±0.54a
Life cycle	6.42±1.14b	9.52±1.91a
Pre-oviposition	1.82±0.83
Oviposition	14.42±3.43
Post-oviposition	3.80±0.30
L i f e s p a n	18.34±3.14b	31.21±2.79a
No. of eggs	19.44±2.79

(Means within in row followed by the same letter are not statistically different, p > 0.05 Duncan's Multiple Range test).

While life cycle recorded 22.3 and 15.8 days for females and males, respectively, when phytoseiid mite *A. swirskii* reared on eggs of *Parlatoria oleae* (Colvee) (Hemiptera:

Diaspididae). at constant temperature 25°C and 70%RH. Life span was 38.85 and 5.6 days for females and males, respectively (Helmy and Sholla, 2022).

2. Number of consumed preys of *Amblyseius swirskii* reared on 1st nymphal instar of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at constant temperature 26±2°C and 70±5% RH.

The average number of 1st instar of *P. solenopsis* consumed by *A. swirskii* female and male larvae, protonymph and deutonymphal stages as shown in Table (2) were 3.82, 2.83, 2.84, 2.11, 6.14, 3.12, 42.51 and 2.38, respectively. The highest mean of

Table (2): Number of consumed preys (Mean ±S.D.) by *Amblyseius swirskii* (Acari: Phytoseiidae) reared on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on temperature 26±2 °C and 70 ± 5 %RH.

Predator stage	No. of consumed prey (Mean±SD)	
	Female	Male
Larva	3.82±0.84a	2.83±0.83b
Protonymph	2.84±0.04a	2.11±0.70ba
Deutonymph	6.14±0.22a	3.12±0.23b
Adult	42.51±3.31a	2.38±2.58b

Means in row followed by the same letter are not statistically different $p > 0.05$ Duncan's Multiple Range test

The present studies found that, the predator *A. swirskii* may help in planning a successful IPM program for the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* in Egypt.

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total prey consumption of females recorded 42.51 of 1st nymphal instar of *P. solenopsis* but 86.37 when *Amblyseius californicus* (McGregor) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) reared on eggs of *Aulacaspis tubercularis* Newstead (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) under 25 °C temperature (Helmy and Sholla, 2019). While the average number of eggs of *P. oleae* when consumed by phytoseiid mite *A. Swirskii* adult females and males 102 and 60 respectively (Helmy and Sholla, 2022).

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Use of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to attract *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae) and enhance its protein-based bait under field conditions

Samira, A. Abd El-Salam and Naglaa, M. Youssef

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

The peach fruit fly (PFF), *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is a polyphagous insect native to tropical Asia and became a serious pest in Egypt attacking a wide range of fruits. The present experiments were conducted in a mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) orchard located in Mansoura district, Dakahlia Governorate, Egypt. This study aimed to evaluate di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an olfactory attractant for PFF adults and evaluate its ability as an enhancer for Buminal (The commercial product of protein-based bait for PFF). Statistically, the efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (As an attractant for PFF adults) increased by its concentration, increased till it reached the range between 2.5 and 3.0%; then, with the increase of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentration its attractiveness decreased. As general, di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate attracted 6.25 PFF females per each male. In another hand, the elapsed time showed an adverse effect on the efficiency of all the tested concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as attractants for PFF except for the concentration of 5%. The obtained data showed that adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to the protein-based bait (Buminal) with a concentration of 2% significantly increased Buminal's efficiency as an attractant to PFF adults with 6.33 folds of the efficiency of Buminal alone.

Introduction

Fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) are of the most economically important groups of insect pests attacking fruits and vegetables over all the world causing large losses (Allwood, 1997 and Abd El-Kareim *et al.*, 2008). As a result of the infestation by these insects, quarantine restrictions are instigated in the infested areas; so that commercial fruits undergo protective and quarantine treatments before export (Vargas *et al.*, 2008). The peach fruit fly (PFF), *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is a

polyphagous insect native to tropical Asia, but it was spread to many regions of the world (Agarwal *et al.*, 1999 and El-Minshawy *et al.*, 1999). In Egypt, PFF became a serious pest attacking a wide range of fruits that differ in their ripening times and that persist almost throughout the year (White and Elson-Harris, 1992).

Nitrogen-containing food sources strongly influence physiology and behaviour of tephritid flies (Yuval *et al.*, 2007). This influence is a result of the female's need for

protein to produce its eggs (Epsky *et al.*, 2014 and Piñero *et al.*, 2015). Hence, protein baits mixed with pesticides have been used to control fruit flies worldwide (Vargas *et al.*, 2001; Barry *et al.*, 2003 and Ghanim, 2018). So, protein-based bait formulations must have good levels of attraction and stimulate adult flies (i.e., PFF) to ingest the lethal doses of the pesticides; then obtain effective suppression against fruit fly populations (Mangan, 2009 and 2014).

Releasing ammonia substances significantly affected the attraction of fruit flies to food sources (Epsky and Heath, 1998 and Hull and Cribb, 2001). This information led to the development of effective ammonia-containing lures (Moustafa and Ghanim, 2008 and Ragab and Youssef, 2021). According to Mazor *et al.* (2002), the attraction level of fruit flies to ammonia-based compounds is known as dose-dependent and the range of attractiveness is very narrow, while the range of repellence is much wider. So, some ammonium compounds (with accurate concentrations) were added to protein-based baits to enhance their effectiveness for fruit flies such as PFF (Moreno and Mangan, 2002 and Piñero *et al.*, 2015). The addition of ammonium compounds to baits or local products led to an improvement in their effectiveness for monitoring and suppression of the populations of fruit flies (Piñero *et al.*, 2015). So, the purposes of this study are:

- 1) Evaluating di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as an olfactory attractant for PFF adults at different concentrations.
- 2) Evaluating its ability as an enhancer for Buminal (The commercial product of protein-based bait) to increase its attractiveness to PFF adults under field conditions.

Materials and methods

The present experiments were done in an area of about 5 feddans (= 21000 m²) of mandarin (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) orchard

in the experimental farm of Faculty of Agriculture, Mansoura University (located at Mansoura district, Dakahlia governorate) by using di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate ((NH₄)₂HPO₄).

1. Chemicals:

Buminal was obtained from Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center. Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate ((NH₄)₂HPO₄) was obtained from Edwic Company, Egypt.

2. Evaluation the efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations as attractants for *Bactrocera zonata*:

Four concentrations (1, 2, 3, and 5% as w: v of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate: water) were used in the present experiment (The concentration of 3% is the recommended one). The modified Nadel traps (Which was described by Hanafy *et al.* (2001) were used by putting 250 milliliters of each concentration inside one trap. All treatments were replicated four times. Traps were hung in a shaded place at a height of about 1.5 on the trees and distributed in a completely randomized design within the wind direction. As interval distance, 20 meters between every two successive traps were considered to avoid interference among traps.

During the period from the 13th to 28th of October 2022 (15 days), every 3 days traps were inspected by filtering the solutions inside traps from PFF adults and solutions were returned to the traps again. Captured females and males of PFF were counted and recorded as captured flies /trap/day (FTD values).

3. Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as enhancer for the efficiency of protein-based baits to attract *Bactrocera zonata*:

The mixture of buminal and (NH₄)₂HPO₄ was prepared first by diluting Buminal with distilled water to obtain the concentration of 5% (vol/vol) and then, used

to prepare 1 and 2% of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate. Buminal 5% without mixing with di-ammonium hydrogen was used as a positive control for comparison. Inside each modified Nadel trap, 250 ml of the mixture was put. Each treatment was replicated four times.

During the period from the 24th of November to the 9th of December 2022 (15 days), the prepared traps were distributed in a completely randomized design as previously mentioned. As an interval period, traps were inspected every three days and the captured females and males were counted and recorded as previously mentioned.

4. Statistical analysis:

To analyze the obtained data followed by the least significant difference (LSD, 0.05), One-way ANOVA was used. In addition, regression analysis was performed. The statistical analysis program CoHort

Software (2004) was used to analyze all analyses.

Results and discussion

1. Evaluation of efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations as attractants for *Bactrocera zonata*:

Data illustrated in Figure (1) showed that the highest activity of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate after 3, 6, 9 and 12 days were recorded at the concentration of 3% (FTDs were 3.82 ± 0.33 , 1.66 ± 0.27 , 3.66 ± 0.90 and 3.80 ± 0.33 , respectively); while the highest activity after 15 days was recorded at the concentration of 5% (FTD was 1.66). On another hand, the highest attraction of 0.5 and 3% concentrations to PFF adults was recorded after 3 and 12 days; while the highest attraction of 1, 2 and 5% was recorded after 12, 6 and 15 days, respectively.

Figure (1): Attractiveness of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations (0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5%) to *Bactrocera zonata* adults all over 15 days under field conditions.

The general means of attracting PFF to di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations all over 15 days showed that the concentration 3% was the significantly highest effective concentration for PFF

adults; while the efficiency of 0.5, 1, 2 and 5% of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate exhibited the second rank in attracting PFF with no significant differences between them (Figure 2).

Figure (2): Mean attracted *Bactrocera zonata* adults to 0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5% di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate all over 15 days under field conditions (Columns had the same letters did not differ at the significantly of 5%).

Figure (3) shows the relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as an attractant to females and males PFF as well as the total of them. The efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate increased by its concentration increased till it reached the range between 2.5 and 3.0%; then, by the increase of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentration its attractancy to PFF decreased.

The statistical relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its attractancy females and males of PFF was determined as follow:

Females: $FTD = -0.14 C^2 + 0.77 C + 0.37$

Males: $FTD = -0.07 C^2 + 0.43 C - 0.18$

Total: $FTD = -0.20 C^2 + 1.19 C + 0.20$

Figure (3): Relationship between the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and its efficiency as attractant to females and males of *Bactrocera zonata* under field conditions.

The obtained data revealed that the highest sex ratio (As number of females per one male) was recorded when the concentration of 0.05% was used (12.71 females) followed by 2% of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (10.25 females/one

male). The general mean number of attracted females per one male in all of the tested di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations all over the tested period was recorded as 6.25 females (Figure 4).

Figure (4): Number of *Bactrocera zonata* adult females per one male attracted to the concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5%) under field conditions.

Figure (5) shows the effect of elapsed time on the efficiency of the tested di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations as attractants for PFF adults all over the tested period. The highest concentration affected by the elapsed time was that of 2% (Where R^2 reached 0.464) followed by 0.5, 5, 3 and 1%, respectively (where R^2 -values were 0.464, 0.204, 120 and

0.025, respectively). In another hand, the elapsed time showed an adverse effect on the efficiency of all the tested concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as attractants for PFF (Where it decreased by the elapsed time) except on the concentration of 5% (Where its efficiency increased by the elapsed time).

Figure (5): Effect of the elapsed time on the efficiency of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations (0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5%) as attractants for *Bactrocera zonata* adults under field conditions all over 15 days.

2. Di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate as enhancer for the efficiency of protein-based baits to attract *Bactrocera zonata*:

As shown in Table (1), adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 1% to Buminal (The food attractant of PFF) with a concentration of increased its efficiency as an attractant to PFF after 3 and 15 days of the starting experiment (Mean FTDs were 0.08 ± 0.16 and 0.58 ± 0.19)

and did not attract in the rest interval periods. While, adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 3% to the same concentration of Buminal increased its efficiency as an attractant to PFF during all the interval periods; however, FTDs were 0.33 ± 0.26 , 0.42 ± 0.14 , 0.08 ± 0.20 , 0.25 ± 0.5 and 0.80 ± 0.50 after 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days of starting the experiment.

Table (1): Enhancement of protein-based bait (Buminal) by using 1 and 2% concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to attract *Bactrocera zonata* under field conditions all over 15 days.

Conc.%	FTD after (in days)					LSD(P=0.05)
	3	6	9	12	15	
0.0	0.00±0.00	0.08±0.20	0.08±0.20	0.17±0.19	0.00±0.00	0.20
1.0	0.08±0.16	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.58±0.19	0.30
2.0	0.33±0.26	0.42±0.14	0.08±0.20	0.25±0.5	0.80±0.50	0.62
LSD(P=0.05)	0.29	0.41	0.22	0.53	0.66	

Adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to the protein-based bait (Buminal) with a concentration of 2% significantly increased Buminal's efficiency as attractant to PFF adults with 6.33 folds of the efficiency of Buminal alone all over the

tested period; while, adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to Buminal with a concentration of 1% significantly did not increase Buminal's efficiency as an attractant to PFF adults (Figure 6).

Figure (6): Mean attracted PFF adults (As FTDs) Buminal alone or enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate 1 and 2% concentrations under field conditions all over 15 days (Columns had the same letters did not differ at the significantly of 5%).

The effect of elapsed time on the efficiency of Buminal alone (As an attractant for PFF adults) or enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at concentrations of 1 and 2% all over the tested period is illustrated in Figure (7). The highest treatment affected by the elapsed time was that of Buminal enhanced with 1% di-

ammonium hydrogen phosphate ($R^2 = 0.391$) followed by enhanced with 2% di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate ($R^2 = 0.206$) and Buminal alone ($R^2 = 0.041$), respectively. In another hand, the elapsed time showed a positive effect on the efficiency of all the tested treatments as attractants for PFF (Where it increased by the elapsed time).

Figure (7): Effect of the elapsed time on the efficiency of the protein-based bait (Buminal) alone or enhanced with di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate concentrations (1 and 2%) as attractants for *Bactrocera zonata* adults under field conditions all over 15 days.

Increases in ammonia produced from protein bacterial degradation were correlated with increases in bait efficiency as an attractant to adults of fruit flies, whereas the high attractiveness of proteinaceous baits to the adults of fruit flies was associated with high release rates of ammonia and vice versa (Bateman and Morton, 1981 and Mazor, 2009). The obtained data showed that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at its concentrations ranged between 2.5 and 3.0% was a good attractant for PFF adults under field conditions. Ghanim *et al.* (2021) reported a similar conclusion, where they found that 2 and 3% of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate are the superior of its concentrations in attracting PFF under field conditions. While Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008) found that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate was superior in its attractiveness to PFF at its concentrations of 1. Also, Moustafa and Ghanim (2008) and Ragab and Youssef (2021) found that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate at its concentration of 3% was superior to its concentrations in attracting *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) under the field conditions.

The lower efficiency of the low concentrations (Less than 2.5%) may be attributed to their lower attractiveness to PFF adults, while the lower efficiency of high concentrations (More than 3%) may be attributed to the appearance of the relative repellency to MFF adults. These suggestions may be explained by the studies of Mazor *et al.* (2002); they mentioned that the attraction level of fruit flies to ammonia-based compounds is known as dose-dependent and the range of attractiveness is very narrow, while the range of repellence is much wider.

Dietary sources of nitrogen showed strong effects on the physiology and behavior of fruit flies (Kaspi *et al.*, 2000 and Yuval *et al.*, 2007). So, baits including ammonia in their formulations have a relatively high efficiency as attractants for fruit flies because

of the advantage of the key role that ammonia plays in fruit fly attraction (Heath *et al.*, 2004 and Leblanc *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, ammonium acetate is added to the food attractant (Biolure) and so it becomes the most attractive component for *C. capitata*. Also, adding ammonium acetate or di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate to the insecticidal bait (GF-120; which considered a protein-based bait) exhibited significant positive effects of its attractiveness to *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae), PFF and *C. capitata* (Piñero *et al.*, 2011 and Ghanim, 2018). In the present study, the commercially protein-based bait of Buminal was enhanced as an attractant to PFF by adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 2% to it, which was found a significant increase in attracting PFF adults. Similar findings were obtained by Hemeida *et al.* (2017); they reported that Buminal could be enhanced by adding di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate and resulting in significant increases in its efficiency as an attractant to PFF under field conditions. Also, the insecticidal bait of GF-120 can be enhanced by di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate with a concentration of 2% to increase its efficiency as an attractant to PFF and *C. capitata* (El-Metwally, 2017 and Ghanim, 2018). Hemeida *et al.* (2017) added that di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (3%) can enhance the commercially protein-based baits of Agrinal or Amadene (5%) to increase their efficiency as attractants for PFF adults.

Females of fruit flies require a source of protein for egg maturation; so, this requirement may probably be the main cause for the strong female attraction to the protein-based baits (Epsky *et al.*, 2014 and Piñero *et al.*, 2015). These findings may support the present results; where, all concentrations of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate tended to attract PFF females more than males. Similarly, Yee (2007), Moustafa and Ghanim

(2008), El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017) found that ammonium compounds attracted females of fruit flies with higher numbers than its males, whereas, adding ammonium compounds to protein baits enhanced the response of fruit fly females more than its males (Piñero *et al.*, 2015).

The present study showed that the efficiencies (As attractant to PFF adults) of di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate (At concentrations 1 and 2%) were the most stable treatment over the past time of 15 days under field conditions (≠f it used lonely or for enhancing the protein-based bait, Buminal). These findings came in the same trends of Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014) and Ghanim *et al.* (2021); whereas they reported that the efficiencies of ammonium compounds in attracting adult fruit flies were stable or tended to increase by the elapsed time under field conditions.

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Effect of planting date of cucumber seedlings on the infestation level by *Aphis gossypii* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) under plastic greenhouses

Abla, F. A. Saad and Gamila, A. M. Heikal

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

A Current study was carried out to show the effect of the planting date of cucumber seedlings *Cucumis sativus* L. on the infestation level by *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) under plastic greenhouses. The study was carried out throughout a comparison between three planting dates (Periods) of cucumber seedlings; Early summer planting during (January-February), Summer planting during (March-April) and Nile planting during (September- October). Experiments were carried out at two different zones (Governorates); Dokki Zone- Greenhouses of Agricultural Research Center (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qaliobya Governorate) during season 2021 under plastic greenhouses. Obtained results show that in both Giza and Qaliobya Governorate the infestation level with *A. gossypii* on cucumber plants at both three successive planting periods was arranged descending as follows, summer planting, early summer planting and Nile planting respectively. While the infestation level with *B. tabaci* on cucumber plants at both three successive planting periods was arranged descending as follows: Nile planting, summer planting and early summer planting respectively. The results obtained were also the same at Qaliobya Governorate. Statistical analysis showed that there were highly significant differences between population numbers of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* on cucumber plants at both the three successive planting dates (Periods) at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during successive season 2021.

Introduction

Cucumber plants *Cucumis sativus* L. belong to the family Cucurbitaceae is a very economically important crop and it is very popular in Europe, The United States, China and many countries all over the world (Plader *et al.*, 2007). And Zhang *et al.* (2009) indicated that cucumber is an economically

important crop and is one of the healthy fruits which have many health benefits. Also, Weng (2021) indicated that cucumber *C. sativus* is a very important vegetable crop worldwide.

Cucumber plants are infested with many different pests, Danna *et al.* (2015) referred to the fact that cucumber is easily

damaged by many pests and aphids. such as *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae) are among the most serious pests in cucumber production and often cause severe loss of yield. Also, Shi *et al.* (2016) referred to *A. gossypii* as one of the most efficient vectors for CMV and causes serious damage to cucumber crops. And Liang *et al.* (2016) indicated that aphids are one of the most serious cucumber pests and frequently cause serious damage to commercially produced crops.

Whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is one of the most damaging pests of cucumber crops grown in open fields and under protected conditions (Shriram and Sangha, 2021). And Yang *et al.* (2004) studied the hosts preference of whiteflies and *B. tabaci* toward many vegetable crops, results indicated that cucumber plants were the most host preference of *B. tabaci*.

A current study was carried out to show the effect of the planting date of cucumber seedlings *C. sativus* on the infestation level by *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* under plastic greenhouses.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental design:

Experiments were conducted on cucumber plants, *Cucumis sativus* L. under plastic greenhouses in two different areas (Governorates), Dokki - Greenhouses of Agricultural Research Center (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qaliobya Governorate) during season 2021. Experiments were carried out in two successive areas under plastic greenhouses. Each plastic greenhouse is divided into two big separate parts, each one isolated from the other by polyethylene wire with holes (0.5 microns). The first part had an artificial infestation with *A. gossypii*, and the second part had an artificial infestation with *B. tabaci*, and each part was divided into five plots (Replicates). The study was carried out

at the two successive locations on three different planting times (Periods) of cucumber (Three planting dates); early summer planting during (January-February), summer planting during (March-April) and Nile planting during (September- October). It is proven accurate observations of the infestation by the two successive insects: *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* numbers (Adults and nymphs) in random samples of the cucumber plants (Leaves) weekly. Direct counting and laboratory counting were done weekly during both the three planting periods (Dates) of cucumber plants at the two successive locations.

2. Statistical analysis:

In the current study population fluctuation of both two successive insects *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* and mean numbers of each one were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the means were compared by L.S.D. test at 0.05 level using SAS program (SAS Institute, 1988).

Results and discussion

A Current study was carried out to study the effect of the planting date of cucumber seedlings *C. sativus* on the infestation level by *A.s gossypii* and *B. tabaci* under plastic greenhouses. The study was carried out throughout a comparison between three planting dates (Periods) of cucumber seedlings; early summer planting during (January-February), summer planting during (March-April) and Nile planting during (September- October). Experiments were carried out at two locations (governorates); Dokki - Greenhouses of Agricultural Research Center (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qaliobya Governorate) during the season 2021 under plastic greenhouses.

1. Early summer planting:

Results obtained and tabulated in Table (1) show population fluctuation in both *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* infesting cucumber seedlings cultivated in Giza and Qaliobya Governorate in the early summer planting (January- February) during season 2021 under greenhouses.

Table (1): Population fluctuations of *Aphis gossypii* and *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber plants at the early summer planting at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during season 2021.

Date	Giza Governorate		Qaliobya Governorate	
	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>
1/ 1/ 2021	17.5	7.5	14.3	5.3
8/ 1/ 2021	19.3	9.8	16.5	7.2
15/ 1/ 2021	21.6	11.3	17.9	8.5
22/ 1/ 2021	23.5	13.4	19.7	10.4
29/ 1/ 2021	25.7	15.1	21.6	12.3
5/ 2/ 2021	27.9	17.3	23.2	13.8
12/ 2/ 2021	29.2	19.4	25.7	15.9
19/ 2/ 2021	31.5	21.7	27.9	17.5
26/ 2/ 2021	33.6	22.9	29.5	18.9
Total	229.8	138.4	196.3	109.8
Mean	25.5	15.4	21.8	12.2
F_(0.05)	325.66	431.84	389.52	463.11
L.S.D	1.025	1.037	1.064	1.075

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

Data obtained show that in Giza Governorate the mean numbers in both *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* were (25.5, 15.4 individual/leaf) respectively whereas at

2. Summer planting:

Results obtained and tabulated in Table (2) show population fluctuation in both *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* infesting cucumber seedlings cultivated both in Giza and

Table (2): Population fluctuations of *Aphis gossypii* and *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber plants at the summer planting at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during season 2021.

Date	Giza Governorate		Qaliobya Governorate	
	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>
1/ 3/ 2021	34.5	23.2	30.5	19.5
8/ 3/ 2021	35.9	24.7	32.7	20.8
15/ 3/ 2021	37.2	25.9	33.9	22.3
22/ 3/ 2021	38.5	27.4	35.4	23.7
29/ 3/ 2021	39.7	28.9	36.9	24.9
5/ 4/ 2021	41.5	30.3	38.3	26.5
12/ 4/ 2021	43.6	31.7	39.8	27.8
19/ 4/ 2021	45.7	32.9	41.5	29.3
26/ 4/ 2021	47.3	34.0	43.2	30.5
Total	363.9	259.0	332.2	225.3
Mean	40.4	28.7	36.9	25.0
F_(0.05)	412.23	385.72	472.33	366.21
L.S.D	1.072	1.063	1.055	1.043

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$)

Data obtained show that in Giza Governorate the mean numbers both of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* were (40.0, 28.7 individual/leaf), respectively. Whereas at Qaliobya Governorate the mean numbers both of

Qaliobya Governorate the mean numbers both of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* were (21.8, 12.2 individual/leaf), respectively.

Qaliobya Governorate in the summer planting (March- April) during season 2021 under greenhouses.

A. gossypii and *B. tabaci* were (36.9, 25.0 individual/leaf) respectively.

3. Nile planting:

Results obtained and tabulated in Table (3) show population fluctuation in both *A.*

gossypii and *B. tabaci* infesting cucumber seedlings cultivated both in Giza and Qaliobyia

Governorate in the Nile planting (September-October) during season 2021 under greenhouses.

Table (3): Population fluctuations of *Aphis gossypii* and *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber plants at the Nile planting at Giza and Qaliobyia Governorates during season 2021.

Date	Giza Governorate		Qaliobyia Governorate	
	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>
1/ 9/ 2021	7	36.7	5.7	33.5
8/ 9/ 2021	8	37.9	6.9	35.8
15/ 9/ 2021	10	39.5	8.3	37.3
22/ 9/ 2021	12	40.9	9.5	38.9
29/ 9/ 2021	13	42.3	10.9	40.1
6/ 10/ 2021	15	45.5	12.3	41.5
13/ 10/ 2021	17	47.6	14.5	43.7
20/ 10/ 2021	19	48.9	16.7	45.9
27/ 10/ 2021	20	50.3	18.5	47.3
Total	121.0	389.6	103.3	364.0
Mean	13.4	43.3	11.5	40.4
F_(0.05)	275.83	344.66	378.11	288.93
L.S.D	1.045	1.067	1.023	1.037

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05)

Data obtained show that in Giza Governorate the mean numbers in both *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* were (13.4, and 43.3 individual/leaf) respectively. Whereas at Qaliobyia Governorate the mean numbers both of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* were (11.5, 40.4 individual/leaf) respectively.

4. Comparison between the infestation by *Aphis gossypii* and *B. tabaci* on cucumber plants on the successive three planting dates (periods) of cucumber:

Data tabulated in Table (4), Figures (1) and (2) show a comparison between population numbers of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* (Total and mean) on cucumber plants in three successive planting periods at Giza and Qaliobyia Governorates during season 2021.

Data obtained showed that at Giza Governorate the infestation level with *A. gossypii* on cucumber plants in the three successive planting dates (Periods) were arranged descending as follows; summer planting, early summer planting and Nile planting respectively. While the infestation level with *B. tabaci* on cucumber plants in the three successive planting dates (Periods) were arranged descending as follows; Nile planting, summer planting and early summer planting respectively. The data was achieved also the same at Qaliobyia Governorate.

Statistical analysis shows that were highly significant differences between population numbers of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* on cucumber plants in the three successive planting dates (Periods) at both Giza and Qaliobyia Governorates during season 2021.

Table (4): Comparison between population numbers of *Aphis gossypii* and *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber plants at both three successive planting dates (Periods) at Giza and Qaliobyia Governorates during season 2021.

Insect	Early summer planting		Summer planting		Nile planting		F _(0.05)	L.S.D
	Giza	Qaliobyia	Giza	Qaliobyia	Giza	Qaliobyia		
<i>Aphis gossypii</i>								
Total	229.8	196.3	363.9	332.2	121	103.3	325.44	1.025
Mean	25.5	21.8	40.4	36.9	13.4	11.5	423.72	1.037
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>								
Total	138.4	109.8	259.0	225.3	389.6	364.0	374.23	1.014
Mean	15.4	12.2	28.7	25.0	43.3	40.4	428.35	1.056

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05)

Figure (1): Comparison between population numbers of *Aphis gossypii* on cucumber plants at both three successive planting dates (Periods) at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during season 2021.

Figure (2): Comparison between population numbers of *Bemisia tabaci* on cucumber plants at both three successive planting dates (Periods) at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during season 2021.

The obtained results agreed with those obtained by Liang *et al.* (2015) in China who indicated that *A. gossypii* is a serious pest to cucumber plants and it has one peak during March-April. Adriaan *et al.* (1994) indicated that *A. gossypii* is seen as in high population in cucumber crops especially in March and April in the open fields and under glasshouses. Also, Mojtaba *et al.* (2010) indicated the performance and population growth rate of the cotton aphid *A. gossypii*

and the yield losses inflicted by that insect, and it has high population numbers during March. Van and Kamh (1995) studied the life history of *A. gossypii* on cucumber plants; the influence of temperature, host plant and parasitism under glasshouses, and indicated that the pest suitable temperature for aphid growing ranged from 25-30°C.

Mohamed (2012) studied the impact of planting dates, spaces and varieties on the infestation of cucumber plants with whitefly,

B. tabaci, through studied comparison between three times of cultivated of cucumber seedlings on 15th March, 15th April and 15th May and found that planting cucumber seedlings on March month was less infested by *B. tabaci* than April and May. Also, Dilip *et al.* (2021) studied the population buildup of whitefly, *B. tabaci* on parthenocarpic cucumber in relation to weather parameters under the protected environment in Punjab and indicated that September month was more suitable for growing and reproduction whitefly than other months.

Hall (2015) studied methods of controlling whitefly, *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and cotton aphid, *A. gossypii* in glasshouses by two isolates of the fungus, *Verticillium lecanii* and indicated that the whitefly had two peaks of population during September and March months. Amna *et al.* (2012) studied the impact of the type of greenhouse cover sheets on certain major cucumber pests under protected cultivation and indicated that the maximum population of aphid and whitefly were observed during May.

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Effect of magnetized water on the bio-efficacy of alpha cypermethrin against *Thrips tabaci*
(Thysanoptera: Thripidae) infesting green onion plants

Mohamed, H. Soliman; Hosnea, A. Afifi; Ola, M. Roshdy and Ahmed, I. Amer
Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

Onion, *Allium cepa* L. belongs to the family Alliaceae and is an herbaceous winter vegetable. Onion is used approximately every day in a large variety of dishes as a fresh salad or added in cooking dishes. *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) causes damage to onions by their rasping and sucking mouth parts affecting both the yield and viability of the seed yield. The water which is used in the spray solution causes degradation to insecticide as a result of heavy metals mixing with water. The specific objectives of the present study were to find out the effectiveness of the water magnetization on bio-efficacy to alpha cypermethrin against thrips infesting green onion compared with normal water. The present investigation was carried out at the Plant Protection Research Station, at Qaha station, Qalyubia governorate, Egypt during the winter 2021–2022. The results of statistical analysis reported that there were significant differences between each treatment in case of initial effect, after 3, 5, 7 and 14 days from spray. Whereas insignificant difference in case of residual effect after two applications. Concerning the first spray, magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin treatment was the most superior recording 85.44 % at initial effect, followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water at 49.24 % and magnetic water recording 21.45 % reduction. The highest reduction of residual effect was 71.58 % for magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water 62.01 %, and magnetic water caused 49.48 % reduction to *T. tabaci* individuals. In the case of second application, concerning immediate annihilation (Initial effect) magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin comes in first order followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetic water and magnetic water, respectively. The paper recommended that from necessary water magnetization before adding alpha cypermethrin.

Introduction

The onion crop *Allium cepa* L. belongs to the family Alliaceae and is

considered one of the important export crops, which is distinguished from other crops in that it grows in most climatic regions of the

world and Egypt. It is considered one of the countries distinguished in the production of onions. Onions are compatible with the environmental and climatic conditions in Egypt with the needs of this crop. It has many advantages that make it occupy a distinguished position among the producing and exporting countries in the global markets (Astley *et al.*, 1982). The total cultivated area of onion is 4057 feddans with an annual production of 57744 tons of bulb with an average of 14.233 ton/feddans (Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation Statistic, 2019).

Onions are infested with many pests including insects (Arkhipove, 1984). The onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera, Thripidae) principally a pest of onion crops. Both nymphs and adults greatly harm the crop, resulting in yield losses of 10–20 % per year and leaf damage of up to 40–60 % (Waiganjo *et al.*, 2008). Onion thrips when fed on leaves cause death in young plants, reduced onion yield, seeds and bulb size. If onion thrips are not controlled, onion yield reduction can reach levels from 34 % to nearly 50 % (Fournier *et al.*, 1995).

Also, the thrips cause environmental problems and remain persistent and active. It is difficult to control this pest by causes its small size and hidden inter and between bulbs leaves habits (Lewis, 1997). Methods of various control using different materials were used to reduce the population of onion thrips below economic injury level (EIL) and to get high production of onions. Groundwater used for irrigation and dilution can contain salts and heavy metals, reducing insecticide efficiency and sedimentation. Magnetically Treated Water (MTW) has many benefits, but it needs to be investigated to clarify its role and biological effects on humans, animals, and plants (Pang and Deng, 2008). Hasaani *et al.* (2015) studied the interaction of magnetic fields with flowing water and found that physical properties such as pH, TDS, EC,

viscosity, surface tension, and thermal conductivity decreased. Water molecules have a small dipole and can be affected by exogenous electric and magnetic fields, leading to changes in conductivity, TDS and pH. (Baker and Judd, 1996). Kotab (2013) found that the magnetic water conditioner increased pH by 15.65 % for 820 minutes of non-stop circulation, while TDS and Hardness were not affected. Biological benefits claimed include increased commercial earliness of crops; increased yield; increased vitamin C, sugar and total acid content and increased flowering and fruit set (Pavlov *et al.*, 1983). Under Egyptian conditions, the application of magnetic technology is a new concept. Guo *et al.*, (1994) reported that magnetizing seeds is very efficient to increase the number of germinating seeds and to hasten the germination process.

Hillal and Hillal (2000) reported that full wheat germination of 100 % was obtained after 6 days for magnetic treatment compared to a rate of 83 % after 9 days for normal practice. They also observed that the germination of pepper seeds was higher with magnetically treated seeds compared to seeds with magnetically treated irrigation water. Cucumber seeds had the highest germination percentage when both irrigation water and seeds were magnetically treated. They also reported that tomato seeds responded more favorably to magnetically treated irrigation water than the magnetically treated seeds. Due to the high price of the water magnetizer, we thought of using a round magnetic pole was low cost. The specific objectives of the present study were to find out the effectiveness of the water magnetization on bio-efficacy to alpha cypermethrin against thrips infesting green onion compared with normal water.

Materials and methods

1. Insecticides: alpha cypermethrin 10 % EC at a rate of 100cm / 100 L of water.

Magnetized water:

Magnetized water was obtained by passing irrigation water on the magnetized water apparatus (2 inch/ 2000 salinity, inner diameter 3 cm - device length 60 cm – strong 5000 Gauss - flow rate 2 m²/hour. In this study, using groundwater from the water well at a depth of 80 meters, the water was collected after a period of half hour from startup, whereon divided the water into two kinds, the first type of groundwater was using magnetized water after 15 minutes from passes during magnetic pole, thenceforth adding of insecticide to magnetized water, the two types from groundwater were normal water without using a magnetic pole.

Onion plants were examined weekly till the appearance of *T. tabaci* above the critical economic threshold limit. A Knapsack sprayer (Dorsal sprayer) was used to spray each treatment alone. The experimental sprayed twice between it was 14 days. Plant samples were taken from each plot, 10 plants were taken and put in paper bags, after that transferred to the laboratory at the station of Plant Protection Research, Qaha, Qalyubia governorate, Egypt to examination. *T. tabaci* adult and nymph were counted and recorded after 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th and 14th day from application, mean and reduction percentages were recorded and statistical analysis was carried out according to Henderson and Tilton (1955) equation. % reduction percentage = $100 * (1 - (Ta * Cb) / (Tb * Ca))$, where:

Ta= number of thrips after spray; Tb= number of thrips before spray.

Ca =number of thrips in the control after spray; Cb = number of thrips in the control before spray.

2. Experimental design:

The present investigation was carried out at plant protection research station, at Qaha, Qalyubia governorate, Egypt, during winter 2021/ 2022 to study and evaluate effect of magnetized water on bio- efficacy to

alpha cypermethrin insecticide against *T. tabaci*, infesting green onion plants at field. The onion field divided into 4 treatments, each treatment was distributed on 12 plots, plot area 1/100 from faddan (42 m²). The treatments distributed on area randomized complete block design. Onion plants (Var. red), date of planting was the last week of December 2021.

3. Statistical analysis:

The reduction percentage of thrips was analyzed by one-way ANOVA and means were compared by using student's least significant difference. Significance level was $P < 0.05$. Analysis was conducted using SAS statistical software (SAS Institute, 2003).

Results and discussion**1. Impact of water magnetization on bio-efficacy of alpha – cypermethrin against *Thrips tabaci*:**

The current study was conducted to know the effectiveness magnetized water on efficiency of alpha cypermethrin 10 % EC against the population of *T. tabaci*. The data regarding the mean number of *T. tabaci* before and after application. The data from (Table 1 and Figure 1) show pre-treatment beginning 156, 216, 239 and 274 individuals of *T. tabaci* at treatments as follows: Magnetized water with alpha cypermethrin treatment, normal water with alpha cypermethrin, control (Normal water) and magnetized water. In the same table, initial effect after 1st day from the application, the results indicated that the population decreased compared with before treatment whereby noticed that less population record 22 individuals when sprayed using magnetized water with alpha cypermethrin, but other treatments were as follows: normal water with alpha cypermethrin record 107, magnetized water record 217 and control (Normal water) record 241 individuals. The same trend occurs at the 3rd and 14th day from spray where adding insecticide to magnetized water come to the first order record of 10 and

181 adults, but these results differed at the 5th and 7th days from spray recorded 28 and 105 individuals as a second order after normal water with alpha cypermethrin which records 8 and 100 individuals while other treatments come after that. In case of, residual effect adding alpha cypermethrin to magnetized

water record less population 81 individuals compared with other treatments normal water +Alpha cypermethrin record 137 individuals, magnetized water record 172.5 individuals and control record 339 individuals, respectively.

Table (1): Mean number of *Thrips tabaci* before and after first spray.

Treatments	Mean number of <i>Thrips tabaci</i> before and post-treatment						Residual effect
	Pre Treatment	Initial effect	3 Days	5 Days	7 Days	14 Days	
Magnetized water	274	217	157	163	170	200	172.5
Magnetized water + Alpha cypermethrin	156	22	10	28	105	181	81.0
Normal water +Alpha cypermethrin	216	107	50	8	100	390	137
Control (Normal water)	239	241	305	315	346	390	339

Figure (1): Mean number of *Thrips tabaci* after first spray.

The results tabulated in (Table 2 and Figure 2) show that each treatment reduces the population of *T. tabaci* after the first spray (Initial effect) contrast with the population before the spray without control treatments. In the case of the initial effect (After the first day from spray) the data illustrate that mixing alpha cypermethrin with magnetic water recorded less population of 40 individuals followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization 52 individuals, magnetic

water 91 individuals and control 397 individuals. On the other hand, the column includes residual effect in the same table and the same Figure (2) the results obvious that treatment of alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water recorded 68 individuals, magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin 85.5 individuals thenceforth magnetic water recorded 89.75 and control (Check) which record 415.5 individuals.

Table (2): Mean number of *Thrips tabaci* before and after second spray.

Treatments	Mean number of <i>Thrips tabaci</i> before and post-treatment						Residual effect
	Pre-treatment	Initial effect	3 days	5 days	7 Days	14 days	
Magnetic water	225	91	51	70	110	128	89.75
Magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin	200	40	29	87	97	129	85.5
Alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water	187	52	34	60	65	113	68
Control (Un-magnetic water)	395	397	400	405	407	450	415.5

Figure (2): Mean number of *Thrips tabaci* after second spray.

2. Reduction percentage of *Thrips tabaci* infesting green onion after first spray by mixing water magnetization with alpha – cypermethrin:

Data in Table (3) show the impact of adding water magnetic to alpha cypermethrin on the reduction percent of *T. tabaci*, the results of statistical analysis reported that there were significantly different treatments in each treatment in the case of initial effect. Whereas, after 3, 5, 7 and 14 days from spray were insignificant differences between treatments and residual effects. The highest reduction

percentage in initial effect was 85.44% for magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin, thenceforth alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water was 49.24 % and magnetic water recorded 21.45 % reduction. Whereas the residual effect of magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin come in first order with a reduction percent 71.58 % followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water 62.01, and magnetic water caused 49.48 % reduction in *T. tabaci* individuals, with non-significant difference.

Table (3): Reduction percentage of *Thrips tabaci* infesting onion as a result after first application of water magnetization with alpha – cypermethrin.

Treatments	Reduction percentage after 1 st application					
	Initial effect	3 Days	5 Days	7 Days	14 Days	Residual Effect
Magnetic water	21.45 c	55.26 c	54.66 c	57.33 ab	58.70 a	49.48 a
Magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin	85.44 a	95.24 a	86.12 b	49.21 b	41.89 a	71.58 a
Alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetization water	49.24 b	81.66 b	97.12 a	67.49 a	14.52 b	62.01 a
F. value	11.9	117.34	73.27	2.76	18.49	1.30
P value	0.0013	0.0001	0.880	0.123	0.001	0.325
LSD 05	18.06	6.12	8.39	17.98	16.91	31.74

3. Reduction percentage of *Thrips tabaci* infesting onion as a result after second application of water magnetization with alpha–cypermethrin:

From displayed the results in Table (4), the statistical analysis shows that there were significant differences between each treatment after application, where that F-value and LSD₀₅ value at initial effect, 3rd day, 5th day, 7th day, 14th day and residual effect record following (33.73 and 6.01), (7.30 and 5.14), (1.88 and 14.41), (4.13 and 14.18), (1.47 and 6.74) and (1.35 and 10.05), respectively. Concerning immediate annihilation (Initial effect) magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin come in the first order recording 80.10 % reduction followed by alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetic water which record 72.33 % reduction and magnetic water with 59.75 % reduction, respectively. On the other side is the same (Table 4).

The results from residual effect recorded 65.99, 63.55 and 60.78 % reductions in *T. tabaci* individuals for alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetic water, magnetic water, and magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin, respectively. These results were in good agreement with that

obtained by Shahin *et al.* (2016) demonstrated the beneficial effects of applying magnetic water treatment on soil and plants. The magnetic treatment of irrigation water plays an important role for the growth parameters of cucumber plants. Magnetic irrigation water and or magnetized seeds significantly increased the germination percentage of tomato, eggplant, squash and cucumber seeds. Morejon *et al.* (2007) observed an increase in germination of *Pinus tropicalis* seeds from 43% in the control to 81% with magnetically treated water. Sohail *et al.* (2018) found that Curacron at 4 ml/L H₂O is recommended against onion thrips and budworm in Swat Valley.

The onion should be regularly checked for the attack of this pest. If the population increases above Economic Injury Level (EIL) of 20 thrips per plant, then the crop should be sprayed with Curacron at recommended dose. Spraying can be repeated if the pest population exceeds this number. Magnetically treated seeds reduce *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) populations and *T. tabaci* with rising exposure time to the magnetic field (Alakhdar *et al.*, 2022).

Table (4): Reduction percentage of *Thrips tabaci* infesting onion as a result after second application of water magnetization with alpha – cypermethrin.

Treatments	Reduction percent after 2 nd application					
	Initial effect	3 Days	5 Days	7 Days	14 Days	Residual Effect
Magnetic water	59.75 c	77.61 b	69.65 a	56.87 b	50.06 a	63.55 a
Magnetic water with alpha cypermethrin	80.10 a	85.68 a	57.57 a	52.92 ab	46.95 a	60.78 a
Alpha cypermethrin with un-magnetic water	72.33 b	82.35 a	68.7 a	66.26 a	46.95 a	65.99 a
F. value	33.73	7.30	1.88	4.13	1.47	1.35
P value	0.0001	0.015	0.214	0.058	0.285	0.313
LSD 05	6.01	5.14	14.41	14.18	6.74	10.05

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Effect of certain factors on population dynamics of *Aphis craccivora* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on common bean *Phaseolus vulgaris* in Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt

**Ali, M. Mansour; Ibrahim, Labib Ibrahim; Mohammed, Abdel- Ghaffar and Hamzah, M. Kamel
Plant Protection Dept., Fac. of Agric., AL-Azhar Univ., Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt.**

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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out to study the population dynamics of *Aphis craccivora* (Koch) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on the common bean *Phaseolus vulgaris* in relation to certain weather factors at Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt. The study was conducted during 2017 and 2018 seasons. This insect is considered a serious pest in the agricultural fields of Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt. The obtained results showed that maximum population of *A. craccivora* was observed in October and November during Nile plantation and in March during Summer plantation of common bean *P. vulgaris* crop. Statistical analysis showed that *A. craccivora* population had a positive correlation with maximum temperature and minimum temperature during Nile plantation in two seasons while this relation was showing a negative correlation with both minimum and maximum temperature in Summer plantation. However, relative humidity had a negative correlation in Nile plantation. But it was a positive correlation in Summer plantation. The combination of climatic factors on *A. craccivora* population density was prenatal as explained by variance which was 29.02% and 45.31% in the Nile and Summer plantation, respectively during season 2017/2018. But it was 52.08% and 16.58% in the Nile and Summer plantations, respectively during season 2018/2019. Hence the information contained in this paper lead to the identification of the proper integrated pest management (IPM) practices for *A. craccivora*.

Introduction

Common bean *Phaseolus vulgaris* (L.) is a leguminous plant that belongs to the family Leguminaceae, it is the most important grain legume for direct human consumption with production more than twice that of the next most important grain legume, chickpea (Gepts *et al.*, 2008).

The cultivated area in Egypt was increased especially for exportation. Whereas the production of green pods of beans was

251279 tons from the cultivated area of 57873 feddans while the dry seeds were 59496 tons from the plants cultivated in 57877 feddans. Egypt occupies the tenth country among the most important exporting countries. The common bean is also a good source of vitamins and minerals. In addition, contains some anti-nutritional factors such as protease inhibitors, tannins and folic acid (Reyes-Moreno and Octavio Paredes-López 1993).

Aphis craccivora (Koch) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) cause damage to *P. vulgaris* crop by using their rasping-sucking mouth parts to abrade the plant epidermis and suck up the exuding plant sap. Sucking-sap insect pests cause much damage to various vegetable crops, they also play an important role as a vector of plant viruses and produce honeydew. Piercing-sucking insects are some of the most damaging pests for *P. vulgaris* producers due to the direct damage caused by feeding which can cause several plant symptoms including plant death and indirect damage caused by piercing plant protective tissues and vectoring many different plant diseases.

The present work aimed to evaluate the effect of certain weather factors on the population dynamics of *A. craccivora* on common bean *P. vulgaris* in Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Field studies:

Field experiments were planned and conducted to study the population fluctuation of *A. craccivora* infesting common bean plants (*P. vulgaris*) at korus village- Ashmoon city, Menoufiya Governorate throughout two successive seasons; (2017/2018) and (2018/2019). The experiments were carried out on two different cultivars of *P. vulgaris* plants (Flantena and Nebraska).

2. Sampling techniques:

The experiment was carried out in a completely randomized design with three replicates (Each replicate 42 m²) for each of the two varieties. Five plants were chosen randomly in five positions (4 corners+ center) and inspected for the pest. When the plants became high, three leaves per plant were selected at three different levels (Low, middle, and high) for insect counting. The individuals of insect on the plant were directly counted under field conditions and their numbers were recorded. The experiment

area 252 m² was divided into two parts for the two varieties (Flantena and Nebraska). Samples were collected randomly at the early morning weekly until the plant harvest.

3. Effect of weather factors on the population fluctuation of the *Aphis craccivora*:

This experiment aimed to obtain accurate information about the effect of both temperatures and RH. on the population fluctuation of the pest. Meteorological recorded data were obtained from <https://www.wunderground.com>. The statistical analyses (Simple correlation and partial regression) of obtained data were performed by using SAS program (SAS, 2003) to test the effect of the weather factors on the population fluctuation of the insect.

Results and discussion

Population fluctuation of *A. craccivora* was studied during both Nile and Summer plantations throughout two seasons.

1. Season (2017/2018):

1.1. Nile plantation:

Data presented in Table (1) and illustrated in Figure (1) show that the first appearance of *A. craccivora* on both Nebraska and Flantena varieties was in the 1st week of October in Nile plantation. The weekly numbers of insects were 30 and 5 individuals, respectively. The insect population increased gradually to give the highest peak in the 3rd week of October with weekly mean numbers of 400 individuals /45 leaves on Nebraska variety.

While the highest number of insects on Flantena variety was recorded in the following week of October with 220 insects. The insect population decreased gradually to reach 64 insects by early December in Nebraska and in the 4th week of November on Flantena 75 insects.

The insect population disappeared by the end of the season in both varieties. Data presented in Table (1), proved that Nebraska

variety harbored more numbers of aphid 1689 insects than that obtained on Flantena 887

insects. Nebraska variety is more susceptible to infestation with aphids than Flantena.

Table (1): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during Nile plantation (2017-2018) season at Korus village- Ashmoon city, Menoufiya Governorate.

Nile plantation 2017- 2018					
Inspection date	Nebraska	Flantena	Humidity (%)	Temperature (° C)	
			Rang	Min	Max
07/10/2017	30	5	57.95	22.14	31.14
14/10/2017	180	15	52.61	22.71	31.85
21/10/2017	400	55	53.94	21.1	29.44
28/10/2017	312	220	62.21	20.14	28.85
04/11/2017	283	188	45.34	20.42	29.28
11/11/2017	210	209	56.75	18.14	25.57
18/11/2017	130	120	62.87	16.28	25
25/11/2017	80	75	62.84	17.14	26
02/12/2017	64	0	60.57	15.14	21.71
09/12/2017	0	0	63	14.28	23.85
Total	1689	887			
Mean	168.9	88.7			

Figure (1): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during Nile plantation (2017\ 2018) season at Korus vallage- Ashmoon city - Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt.

1.2. Summer plantation:

Data presented in Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (2) showed that the first appearance of the aphid was observed on 24th of March in the case of Nebraska variety with a weekly mean number of 20 individuals.

However, the insect was recorded one week early on Flantena variety by a weekly number of 7 individuals. The aphid population increased gradually to reach the

highest peak on 7th of April with mean numbers of 72 and 35 individuals in Nebraska and Flantena, respectively.

Another peak of aphid population was observed on Nebraska variety, by 21st of April. The aphid population then started to decline until the end of the season. It is obvious from data presented in Table (2) that Nebraska variety harbored more aphids than Flantena variety. The total numbers of aphid

were 237 and 82 individuals on Nebraska variety, and Flantena variety, respectively. In other words, Nebraska variety is more

susceptible to the infestation of *A. craccivora*, than the other variety.

Table (2): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during summer plantation (2017-2018) season at Korus, village- Ashmoon, city, Menoufiya, Governorate.

Summer plantation 2017\2018			Humidity (%)	Temperature (° C)	
Inspection date	Nebraska	Flantena	Avg	Min	Max
10/3/2018	0	0	38.85	17.42	29.57
17/3/2018	0	7	58.72	15.42	24.57
24/3/2018	20	13	32.38	17.42	32.14
31/3/2018	45	19	47.88	15.71	26.57
07/4/2018	72	35	58.07	15.28	26.57
14/4/2018	35	8	44.78	17.71	28.42
21/4/2018	53	0	39.04	20	32.14
28/4/2018	12	0	55.08	17.42	26.71
05/5/2018	0	0	32.25	23.57	36.28
12/5/2018	0	0	50.34	21.14	31
Total	237	82			
Mean	23.7	8.2			

Figure (2): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during summer plantation (2017- 2018) seasons at Koras, vantage- Ashmoon, city – Menoufiya, Governorate, Egypt.

2. Season (2018/2019):

2.1. Nile plantation:

Data presented in Table (3) and illustrated in Figure (3) showed that the first appearance of *A. craccivora* on Flantena variety was observed in the 4th week of September in Nile plantation. The weekly number of insects was 17, while it was 27 insects in Nebraska in the 1st week of October. The insect population increased

gradually week by week to give the highest peak in the 3rd week of October with weekly numbers of 210 in Nebraska. However, the highest weekly number of the pest was recorded in the 2nd week of October by 146 individuals on Flantena. The insect population decreased gradually during November in both Nebraska and Flantena. The insect population disappeared by the end of the season in both varieties.

Table (3): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during Nile plantation (2018-2019) season at Korus village- Ashmoon city, Menoufiya Governorate.

Nile plantation 2018/2019			Humidity (%)	Temperature (° C)	
Inspection date	Nebraska	Flantena	Avg	Min	Max
20\9\2018	0	0	53.87	20.71	32.85
27\9\2018	0	17	59.82	20.28	32.57
04\10\2018	27	55	60.54	24.71	34.42
11\10\2018	177	146	59.82	22.71	30.57
18\10\2018	210	88	57.24	21	28.85
25\10\2018	183	92	47.14	22.42	31.57
01\11\2018	95	27	48.55	18.57	28.42
08\11\2018	14	18	55.54	18.28	28.14
15\11\2018	0	0	60.77	17.28	24.85
22\11\2018	0	0	62.15	13.85	25.14
Total	706	443			
Mean	70.6	44.3			

Figure (3): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during Nile plantation (2018/2019) season at Korus village- Ashmoon city - Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt.

2.2. Summer plantation:

Data presented in Table (4) and illustrated in Figure (4) showed that infestation with *A. craccivora* on the plants was observed at early of March on Nebraska variety. The insect population increased gradually to give the highest peak in the 3rd week of March with a weekly number of 604 in Nebraska. While on Flantena the best infestation started in the 3rd week of March. The insect population increased gradually to give the highest peak in the 4th week of March with a weekly number of 47 insects. The insect fluctuated and disappeared by the end of season.

The obtained data seem to have corresponded to the results of El-Defrawi *et al.* (2000) in Egypt, who observed that the population density of the cowpea aphid *A. craccivora* had two main periods of activity, highest counts were recorded during the third week of December and February season, and during the fourth week of December and third week of March in the second season. Similar findings were reported by Also, Ekram *et al.* (2019) who stated that the highest total

number was recorded by *A. craccivora* and the lowest total number was recorded by *Ophiomyia phaseoli* (Tryon) (Diptera: Agromyzidae). The highest total number recorded during spring seasons in both 2017 and 2018, was represented by *A. craccivora* and the lowest number was by *O. phaseoli*. However, Gamila *et al.* (2016) reported that *A. craccivora* showed a peak of population density during two seasons of study.

While El-Dash *et al.* (2018) cleared that the Summer season had the highest abundance of *A. craccivora* on green bean plants. Helaly *et al.* (1982) in Egypt, studied the population fluctuation of *A. craccivora* on two commonly cultivated varieties of cowpea (Fertriat and Azmerly) and during two plantations in Summer and Nile. They found that the infestation started after 30 – 92 days from sowing date in the summer plantations and after 28 days in the Nili plantations. The aphid population reached a peak on 22 of August and 4 of September for Fertriat variety and on 17 of July and 15 of August for Azmerly variety in the first and second seasons of 1979, 1980, respectively.

Table (4): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during summer plantation (2018-2019) season at Korus, village-Ashmoon, city, Menoufiya, Governorate.

Summer plantation 2018/2019			Humidity (%)	Temperature (° C)	
Inspection date	Nebraska	Flantena	Avg.	Min.	Max.
02/03/2019	63	0	60.78	12.28	20.71
09/3/2019	194	0	54.65	13.14	23.28
16/3/2019	604	20	58.25	13.85	23.42
23/3/2019	310	47	47.78	15.28	24.57
30/3/2019	98	21	53.64	12.14	22
06/4/2019	25	33	45.75	16.85	27.28
13/4/2019	35	12	52.37	15.57	25.71
20/4/2019	14	0	48.84	14.71	26
27/4/2019	2	0	40.41	20.28	33.28
04/5/2019	1	0	46.54	17.42	28.85
Total	1346	133			
Mean	134.6	13.3			

Figure (4): Weekly mean numbers of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean varieties (Nebraska and Flantena) during summer plantation (2018-2019) seasons at Koras vallyage- Ashmoon city - Menoufiya Governorate, Egypt.

3. The effect of weather factors on the population fluctuations of *Aphis craccivora* on common bean:

Statistical analysis of data obtained in (2017/2018) Nile plantation which is illustrated in Table (5) indicated that a simple correlation between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and daily maximum temperature was positive and insignificant correlation coefficient, while daily minimum temperature had a positive and significant effect on the numbers of this insect. However, the daily relative humidity recorded a negative and highly significant influence on the insect numbers ($r=-0.05$). In the Summer plantation simple correlation coefficient between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and daily maximum temperature was negative and insignificant, while daily minimum temperature had a negative and significant correlation with the insect numbers. On the other hand, the daily relative humidity had a positive and insignificant effect on the numbers of this insect ($r=0.15$). In Nile plantation the partial regression value mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and daily maximum temperature was negative and significant, while daily minimum

temperature had a positive and significant effect on the numbers of this insect. The daily relative humidity had a negative and highly significant effect on the numbers of insect *A. craccivora* in season (2017/2018). In summer plantation, the partial regression between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and daily maximum temperature was positive and highly significant, while daily minimum temperature had a negative and highly significant effect on the numbers of this insect. Also, the daily relative humidity had a positive and highly significant effect on the numbers of this insect. In the 2nd season (2018/2019), Nile plantation data in Table (5), showed that a simple correlation between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and both daily maximum and minimum temperature had a positive, however, it was insignificant effect for maximum temperature, but it was a highly significant effect in case of minimum temperature. While the daily relative humidity recorded a negative and significant effect ($r=-0.28$). The partial regression analysis gave a positive and highly significant relation between daily mean minimum temperature and mean numbers of

A. craccivora. Values were negative and highly significant for each of the daily mean maximum temperatures, and RH.%.

In the Summer plantation data obtained the simple correlation between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and daily maximum temperature was negative and significant while daily minimum temperature had a negative and highly significant correlation with the insect numbers. On the other hand, the daily relative humidity had a positive and highly significant effect on the numbers of this insect $r = (0.32)$. The partial regression analysis of (2018/2019) season summer plantation gave a positive and insignificant effects between the mean

numbers of *A. craccivora* and the daily mean maximum temperatures. But the relations were positive and insignificant effect correlation between mean numbers of *A. craccivora* and the daily mean minimum temperature. On the other hand, the daily relative humidity had a positive and highly significant effect on the numbers of this insect. The combination of climatic factors on *A. craccivora* population density was prenatal as explained by variance which was 29.02% and 45.31% in the Nili and Summer plantation during season 2017/2018. But it was 52.08% and 16.58% in Nili and summer plantation during season 2018/2019.

Table (5): Statistical analysis of the effect of some ecological factors on the population of *Aphis craccivora* during seasons (2017/2018) and (2018/2019) on common bean varieties at Korus, village- Ashmoon, city- Menoufiya, Governorate.

Years	Season	<i>Aphis craccivora</i>							
		Factors	Simple correlation		Partial Regression		F. value	P.	E.V. %
			r.	P.	b.	P.			
2017/2018	Nile	Temp. Max.	0.09	0.25	-2.43	0.0162	13.8	<.0001	29.02
		Temp. Min.	0.024	0.0041	2.53	0.0124			
		R.H.%	-0.05	<.0001	-4.71	<.0001			
	Summer	Temp. Max.	-0.12	0.179	3.73	0.0003	21.75	<.0001	45.31
		Temp. Min.	-0.29	0.001	-3.94	0.0001			
		R.H.%	0.15	0.1101	3.33	0.0012			
2018/2019	Nile	Temp. Max.	0.17	0.0861	-5.99	<.0001	26.6	<.0001	52.08
		Temp. Min.	0.497	<.0001	9.28	<.0001			
		R.H.%	-0.28	0.004	-3.16	0.0021			
	Summer	Temp. Max.	-0.23	0.015	0.43	0.6657	5.22	0.0007	16.58
		Temp. Min.	-0.24	0.008	0.05	0.9613			
		R.H.%	0.32	0.0005	3.03	0.0031			

E.V. (%): Explained variance. r: Simple correlation P: Probability value b: Partial regression coefficient value.

Similar findings were reported by Kuroli *et al.* (1999) who studied species distribution, dominance relationships and population density of aphids (Aphidoidea) flying over faba bean fields from 1982-98. The flight activity of 24 aphid species was observed. Among them, the species representing a risk to the faba bean crop were

Acyrtosiphon pisum (Harris), *Aphis fabae* Scopoli, *A. craccivora*, *Macrosiphum euphorbiae* (Thomas) and *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: Aphididae). The number of individuals differed yearly, depending on air temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall. Also, Elango *et al.* (2023) studied the impact

of weather factors on the insect populations and showed that minimum temperature negatively correlated with aphids ($r=0.189$).

Sharmin *et al* (2021) studied that aphid negatively showed a correlation with temperature and rainfall, and a positive correlation with relative humidity, and the correlations were not significant. Multiple regression equation showed that temperature had the highest effect which contributed 16.1 - 19.2% role on the population of aphid.

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Relation between different temperature and resistance to oraganic spinosad of *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae)

El-Ashram, D.¹; Ghada, M.A. Morsi² and Salma, K.H.R.²

¹Organic Agriculture Central Laboratory, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

²Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

Spinosade is one of the compounds recommended for use in biological control programs for fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae), due to its effectiveness, especially in young larval ages. In this study, we shed light on the extent of resistance of the fourth larval age to this compound and the extent of the effect of temperature on the effectiveness of the compound spinosade and on the degree of resistance to this compound. The information we found in this study indicates that the effects of the spinosad compound against the fourth larval instar of fall armyworm *S. frugiperda* differed according to different temperatures and concentrations, as the death rate reached its lowest rate, as it recorded 20.9 % in the resistant strain, at a concentration of 0.2ml/l. at a temperature of 25°C, but when increased temperature and concentration increase The death rate of the resistant strain reached 68.1% at a concentration of 3ml/l. and a temperature of 30°C. Showed that the rectifier coefficient that tested strain (RR) was (8.34 fold) when exposed to a temperature of 30°C, and the value of LC50 was (0.8343). Indicated that the rectifier coefficient that tested strain (RR) increased with decreasing temperature, as the RF was (13.1) at a temperature of 25°C, and value of LC50 was (1.345), the results show that the rate of decrease in the LC50 value reaches -2.5 in the sensitive strain, but in the resistant strain, it was different with different temperatures, as it ranged from -1.9, -1.6 and 1.4 at temperatures 30, 25 and 20°C. The higher the temperature with high concentration, the greater the toxicity of the spinosad compound, and vice versa. .

Introduction

Spodoptera frugiperda (Smith) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) is an economically important insect in Egypt. It attacks many agricultural crops, especially in Upper Egypt,

including corn and sugar cane, causing severe damage in terms of the quantity and quality of crops, and because it is rapidly spreading and multiplying, its ability to infect and deteriorate crops have increased.

The level of infection by *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae over 55 % caused 15-73 % in crops (Hruska and Gould, 1997). The use of chemical pesticides from different groups in the control of the larvae of this insect, especially the fourth larval age, led to the emergence of resistance. Organophosphates and Pyrethroids are the most used in Africa, due to resistance or this larvae to these insecticides (Abrahams *et al.*, 2017). The evolution of resistance in insect populations is quickly becoming a global agricultural problem and poses threats and causes danger to human health (Tabashnik, 2013).

Insect resistance to various pesticides is due to many reasons, including the ability of the insect to destroy the pesticide or the occurrence of structural changes in the insect's body that prevent the pesticide from reaching the site of impact.

Spinosad is a natural compound produced from the fermentation of soil bacteria *Saccaropolyspora spinosa*. Its toxicity to insects is due to its effect on the insect's nervous system. It is similar in the way it affects other chemical compounds such as (Thiamethoxam, imidacloprid, acetamiprid and dinotefuran). Spinosad has two modes of action, the first mode of action by effect of the nicotinic acetylcholine receptors located at the postsynaptic cell junctures, which results in excitation of the insect central nervous system, paralysis and death, the second mode of action is affecting GABA-gated ion channels (Raymond, 2019).

As a result of exposure of the armyworm larvae to high and different doses for long periods of different pesticides, the characteristic of resistance appeared which requires a study to clarify the extent of the resistance of those larvae in terms of the effect of different concentrations on the larvae of the fourth age of the armyworm under different of temperatures.

Materials and methods

1. Insects:

Samples of maize crop infested with fall armyworm larvae were collected from Assiut Governorate in Egypt. The samples

were transferred to the laboratory and the fourth instar larvae of armyworm were selected in preparation for different concentrations of spinosad compound. After transferring the larvae to the laboratory, they were placed in glass jars covered with a layer of transparent cloth under laboratory temperature conditions from 25 to 28°C. In this study, the sensitive strain that was bred under laboratory conditions and away from any chemical pesticides was used to measure the resistance coefficient.

2. Bioassay:

In this experiment, five different concentrations of spinosad compound, Tracer 24% SC (0.2-0.4 -0.8-1.5-3 ml/l.) were used on the field strain and the sensitive strain, under three different temperatures, which are 20°C, 25°C and 30°C. Five different concentrations of Tracer 24%SC compound (Spinosad) were prepared. Each concentration contained three replicates, and each replicate contained 50 larvae of the fourth larval age. The larvae were placed on castor leaves that had been previously sprayed with the previous concentrations. The death rate was calculated after 24 hrs. of treatment at different temperatures.

3. Analysis:

The corrected death rate was calculated using Abbott's formula, (1925), calculating the LC50 and LC90 concentrations using the Iddline-Ehab program, according to Finney (1971). The factor resistance (RF) was calculated by LC50 of the resistant strain / LC50 of the susceptible strain (Wearing and Calhoun, 2005). Temperature coefficient (higher of LC50/ lower of LC50) according to Musser and Shelton (2005).

Results and discussion

In Table (1) the results show that the highest death rate was for the susceptible strain, which reached 91.1 % at a concentration of 3ml/l. of spinosad compound, at a temperature of 30°C. The table also shows that the lowest death rate was recorded for the resistant strain (RR), as it was 20.9% at a concentration of 0.2 ml/l. of spinosad compound at a temperature of 25°C. Table (1) also indicates

that a rise in temperature to 30, increased the mortality rate, reaching 68.1 for resistant strain and 91.1 for sensitive strain at a concentration of 3 ml/l.

Table (1): Effect of different temperatures on response of *Spodoptera frugiperda* strains after treated with different concentrations of spinosad after 24 hrs.

Strains	Concentration (MI/L.)	Mortality% after 24 hrs.		
		30C	25	20 25
S.S.	0.2	56.1	58.9	58.9
	0.4	69.8	69.3	65.7
	0.8	78.0	76.0	78.0
	1.5	89.3	81.5	80.9
	3.0	91.1	88.0	88.9
R.S.	0.2	36.5	20.9	32.1
	0.4	41.2	34.4	39.9
	0.8	48.1	49.9	42.5
	1.5	50.3	51.0	50.0
	3.0	68.1	60.9	60.5

S.S: Sensitive stain, R.S: Resistant strain.

Table (2) shows that the rectifier coefficient that tested strain (RR) was (8.34 fold) when exposed to a temperature of 30C and the value of LC50 was (0.8343) with Slope (0.6670±0.138) and χ^2 (df) were 3.4123(7.8).

Table (2): Different responses of *Spodoptera frugiperda* strains after treated with deferent concentrations of spinosad under a temperature of 30° C.

Strains	Concentrations (MI/L.)	N	LC50 (95%CL)ml/l..	2 χ (df)	Slope±S.D	RF
S.S.	0.2	50	0.1(0.0718-0.2221)	0.5366 (6)	1.1766±0.217	-
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				
R.S.	0.2	50	0.8343(0.5539-1.2891)	3.4123 (7.8)	0.6670±0.138	8.34
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				

S.S: Sensitive strain; R.S: Resistant strain; N: Total number of larvae of the fourth larval age; Cl: Confidence interval; RF: Resistant facror.

Table (3) indicated that the rectifier coefficient that tested strain (RR) increased with decreasing temperature, as the RF was (13.1) at a temperature of 25C, and the value of LC50 was (1.345) with Slope (0.8297±0.141) and χ^2 (df) were 3.4809 (7.8).

Table (3): Different responses of *Spodoptera frugiperda* strains after treated with deferent concentrations of spinosad under a temperature of 25° C.

Strains	Concentrations (MI/L.)	N	LC50 (95%CL)ml/l..	χ^2 (df)	Slope±S.D	RF
S.S.	0.2	50	0.102(0.0309-0.1859)	0.1892 (7.8)	0.8052±0.154	-
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				
R.S.	0.2	50	1.345(0.9775-2.099)	3.4809 (7.8)	0.8297±0.141	13.1
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				

S.S.: Sensitive stain; R.S: Resistant strain; N: Total number of larvae of the fourth larval age; Cl: Confidence interval; RF: Resistant facror.

Table (4) indicated that the rectifier coefficient that tested strain (RR) increased with decreasing temperature, as the RF was (14.3) at a temperature of 20°C, and the value of LC50 was (1.29) with Slope

(0.5866±0.114) and χ^2 (df) were 0.6591 (7.8). The results show that the lower the temperature, the greater the resistance of the larvae to the spinosad compound.

Table (4): Different responses of *Spodoptera frugiperda* strains after treated with deferent concentrations of spinosad under a temperature of 20°C.

Strains	Concentrations (MI/L.)	N	LC50 (95%CL) ml/l..	χ^2 (df)	Slope±S.D	RF
S.S.	0.2	50	0.09(0.0304-0.1803)	0.1670 (7.8)	0.8222±0.155	-
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				
R.S.	0.2	50	1.29(0.8355-2.6114)	0.6591 (7.8)	0.5866±0.114	14.3
	0.4	50				
	0.8	50				
	1.5	50				
	3.0	50				

S.S.: Sensitive stain; R.S: Resistant strain; N: Total number of larvae of the fourth larval age; Cl: Confidence interval; RF: Resistant facor.

Table (5) the results show that the rate of decrease in the LC50 value reaches -2.5 in the sensitive strain, but in the resistant strain, it was different with different temperatures,

as it ranged from -1.9, -1.6 and 1.4 at temperatures 30, 25 and 20°C. The higher the temperature, the greater the toxicity of the spinosad compound, and vice versa.

Table (5): Rate of decrease in LC50 and temperature coefficient to *spodoptera frugiperda* strains after treated with spinosad.

Strain	T (C)	RD	TC	
			5°	10°
S.S.	30	-2.5	0.002	0.01
	25	-2.5		
	20	-2.5		
R.S.	30	-1.9	0.51	0.44
	25	-1.6		
	20	-1.4		

T: Temperature (C); RD: Rate of decrease in LC50 [(log(final LC50 – initial LC50)/N)]; Temperature coefficient (higher of LC50/ lower of LC50).

From the obtained results, the recommended concentration of spinosad compound did not have an effective effect on the fourth age larvae of the fall armyworm *S. frugiperda*. Therefore, the concentration was doubled to calculate the extent of resistance of these larvae. The results also show that temperatures influence the degree of larval resistance to this compound, as it was observed that the resistance to spinosad compound increases whenever the larvae of the fourth age of fall armyworm are exposed to a higher temperature, as the higher the

temperature, the greater the resistance to these larvae.

The results obtained in this study are consistent with Bird *et al.* (2022) who found that the response of 11 field strains of *S. frugiperda* was very low to spinotoram ,spinosad and indoxacarb. Laboratory and field larvae of *S. frugiperda* resistance were also recorded in South and Central America (Okuma *et al.*, 2018). Lira (2019) provided information that the inherited resistance of *S. frugiperda* to spinosad compound was a result of genetic changes and defects in

growth because of exposure to this compound.

The characteristic of resistance in larvae of *S. frugiperda* also appeared in Brazil because of the use of spinosyns in controlling these larvae on maize and Bt-maize plants for long periods, which increased the risk of increasing resistance in this insect (Burtet *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, the tracer analysis of the inherited resistance to the spinosyns gives important and useful information when developing strategies for the effect of the spinosyns group when controlling fall armyworm.

Seham (2023) concluded that when the temperature increased from 15 to 30, the toxicity of the compound spinosad increased against the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and that the resistance decreased, respectively, at temperatures 15, 20, and 25°C, and these results are consistent with this study.

To conclude, the resistance of the armyworm, *S. frugiperda* to the spinosad compound is affected by the temperature, as increasing the temperatures increases the effectiveness of the spinosad against the armyworm, and thus the resistance decreases and vice versa.

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- Raymond A. C. (2019):** Raymond A. Cloyd is State Extension Leader for

Entomology, and Professor and Extension Specialist in Horticultural Entomology/Plant Protection for Kansas State University in Manhattan, Kansas. He can be reached at (785) 532-4750 and rcloyd@ksu.edu.

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Field evaluation of some insecticides on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) larvae and the predator *Chrysoperla carnea* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) as well as their effect on roots and sugar level on sugar beet crop

Hend, A. A. Gad

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

The efficacy of lufenuron, bancoron 20 % EC, pyridalyl, benadryl 10 % EC and chlorfenapyr, salingersuper 24 % SC were evaluated in the field for controlling *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and their side effects on *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph.) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) populations, in addition to sugar beet yield throughout 2021 and 2022 seasons. The tested compounds were sprayed at the recommended dose proposed by Agricultural Pesticide Committee (APC). Findings revealed that bancoron incidence had a reduction in *S. littoralis* larvae by 73.02 and 78.75 % during the two seasons, respectively. Also, it caused a reduction in the predator, *C. carnea* populations with 23.40 and 19.46 % in the two seasons, respectively. In such concern, the conventional insecticides (Benadryl and salingersuper) induced a reduction in *C. carnea* ranging between 84.95 to 92.21 %. Moreover, the findings indicated that there were insignificant differences between treated plots with bancoron and conventional insecticides in root and sugar yield of sugar beet during the two seasons. Considering these results, lufenuron is the preferred insecticide in controlling *S. littoralis* larvae and maintaining *C. carnea* populations in comparison with conventional ones. Also, the three insecticides have the same yield.

Introduction

Sugar beet, *Beta vulgaris* L. (Family: Chenopodiaceae) is grown commercially for sugar production mostly in temperate regions, due to its high sucrose content in roots. Also, this crop is a promising alternative energy source for ethanol production (Rashid, 1999). Sugar beet is used

extensively in the sugar industry in Egypt, providing about 40% of the world sugar production. Nowadays, sugar beet is represented as the first source of sugar in Egypt, from 2014 until now (Anonymous, 2022).

The annual cultivated area of sugar beet is about 700000 feddans. Sugar beet

plants are subject to attack by several insect pests from seed germination up to harvest (Saleh *et al.*, 2009; Abou-El Kassem, 2010 and Bazazo and Hassan, 2021). Among the most important of them is *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Khalifa, 2018). *S. littoralis* is one of the most dangerous insects that infest sugar beet crops, mainly the early plantations (August and September) which may need to be replanted or abolished. In addition, this insect causes great losses in the quantity and quality of sugar beet crops (Amine *et al.*, 2022). It became a destructive pest for sugar crops, causing high economic damage (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2011).

In Egypt, because of the relatively high temperature throughout August and September, *S. littoralis* severely attack the seedling of the sugar beet crop, causing large bare batches in the field and resulting in high economic losses (El-Mahalawy, 2011). In addition, Said *et al.* (2012) reported that *S. littoralis* is considered as one of the important insects in sugar beet crops. It is active almost all year round. In such concern, Mesbah (1984) in a laboratory study, estimated the leaf area of sugar beet consumed by the entire larval stage of *S. littoralis* as 239.26 cm²/larvae. Usually, this pest is controlled by using many conventional insecticides which often result in numerous bad and undesirable side effects such as environmental pollution, resistance appears in the target pests and reducing natural enemies. Insecticide resistance is a major problem in the management of this insect because it has developed resistance to many insecticides (Su and Sum, 2014). On the other hand, it was recommended to use new chemistry insecticides that proved to be preferable to conventional insecticides due to their novel mode of action with less eco-toxicity (Che *et al.*, 2013). Insect growth regulators (IGRs) such as lufenuron represent a class of insecticides favorable mammalian and non-

toxic to natural enemies (Gogi *et al.*, 2006). Lufenuron, a phenyllbenzoyl urea, is a chitin synthesis inhibitor. It is used to control lepidopterous, dipterous, and coleopterous pests, at the same time is considered compatible with natural enemies (Liopis *et al.*, 2004).

For all previous reasons, the present study was designed to evaluate the efficacy of lufenuron on *S. littoralis* larvae, the predator *C. carnea* and sugar beet yield in comparison with conventional insecticides. Numerous investigators demonstrated that *C. carnea* larvae are effective method for controlling *S. littoralis* (eggs and larvae) in Egyptian sugar beet fields (El-Khouly, 2006; Shalaby, 2012 and Al-Habshy, 2018).

Materials and methods

These field trials were done during the two successive seasons 2021 and 2022 at the experimental farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. Nader sugar beet variety was planted on the 15th and 16th of September during the two seasons, respectively. The experimental plots received recommended agricultural practices. Three insecticides were sprayed (Table 1). One of them was lufenuron and the others were with conventional insecticides pyridalyl and chlorfenapyr.

Each insecticide was replicated four times (3x4=12 replicates) in addition to four replicates as a control (Check). Each replicate measured 42m². A completely randomized block design was assigned (CRBD).

Knapsack sprayer (Zol volume) was used for spraying these insecticides. The date of spraying was 15th and 16th October throughout the two seasons, respectively. Inspection of 10 plants/replicate was carried out just before the application and after one, 7 and 10 days post treatment for conventional insecticides. While three, 7 and 10 days after spraying for lufenuron according to Anonymous (2020). Numbers of larvae of

S. littoralis and *C. carnea* larvae were counted by the visual record in the field before and after one, 3, 7 and 10 days post spraying. After 3, 7 and 10 days for IGRs. While 1, 7 and 10 days for conventional insecticides.

Statistical analysis:

Reductions in insect larvae were calculated through Henderson and Tilton, 1955 formula as follows:

$$\text{Reduction \%} = 1 - \left\{ \frac{N.Co.before}{N.Co.after} \times \frac{N.T.after}{N.T.before} \right\} \times 100$$

N: Larvae numbers Co: Control T: Treatment

- Differences between means were done using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $p= 0.05$ using Minitab v.16 software (Duncan, 1955).

Estimation of root and sugar yield:

The roots of treated and check plots (168 m²) were weighed after harvest to determine the root yield per feddan. In addition to, sugar content (%) was determined by using a sucrometer device according to the Association of Official Analysis Chemists (1990), at the laboratory of sugar crops research department, Sakha Agricultural Research Station to estimate sucrose content (%) and calculate the sugar yield per feddan.

Table (1): Certain insecticides sprayed against *Spodoptera littoralis* during 2021 and 2022 seasons.

Common name	Trade name	Category	Rate/fed.
Lufenuron	Bancoron 20% EC	IGRs	40 cm ³
Pyridalyl	Benadryl 10% EC	Conventional	250 cm ³
Chlorfenapyr	Salinger super 24% SC	Conventional	100 cm ³

Results and discussion

1. Effect of certain insecticides (Lufenuron, pyridalyl and chlorfenapyr) on *Spodoptera littoralis* and *Chrysoperla carnea*:

In both seasons, data presented in Tables (2 and 3) clarify that lufenuron caused a reduction in *S. littoralis* larvae with 73.02 and 78.75% in the two seasons, respectively. In such concern the same previous insecticide caused a reduction in the predator, *C. carnea* populations with 23.40 and 19.46% in the two seasons, respectively. Concerning the conventional insecticides, the elimination in *S. littoralis* larvae was 88.66 and 90.97% for pyridalyl in the two seasons, respectively.

Also, the values were 84.07 and 85.55% for chlorfenapyr in the two seasons, respectively. On the other hand, pyridalyl caused a reduction in *C. carnea* with 88.66 and 90.97% in the two seasons, respectively. While chlorfenapyr induces a reduction in *C. carnea* with 92.21 and 84.95% in the two seasons, respectively. James (2004) reported that IGRs are generally considered

compatible with natural enemies conservation.

Also, Naranjo *et al.* (2004) showed that the use of these IGRs could further facilitate biologically based management in agro ecosystems. In another study, Carmo *et al.* (2010) demonstrated that the IGRs are usually regarded as less harmful to beneficial insects, when compared to other chemical groups, mainly conventional insecticides. In addition, Lopez and Osuna (2020) indicated that effective plant protecting programs seek to increase compatibility between control methods including between chemical and biological methods.

Pesticides that are safer for the environment and have low toxicity to natural enemies are more useful in IPM. IGRs are an option for use in IPM and their use has increased, especially chitin synthesis inhibitors.

Lastly, these results showed that lufenuron reduces *S. littoralis* larvae with acceptable value, at the same time conserves *C. carnea* populations in comparison with conventional insecticides.

Table (2): Reduction in *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae due to applied lufenuron and conventional insecticides in 2021 and 2022 seasons.

Compound	Before spray	After one day		Three days		7 days		10 days		Overall mean
	M.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.*	Red.	
2021										
Bancoron	20.00	---	---	10.75	53.26	5.5	78.21	3.75 ^a	87.6	73.02
Benadryl	20.25	5.0	76.76	---	---	4.25	83.37	2.5 ^b	91.83	83.98
Salinger super	20.25	5.5	74.43	---	---	4.00	84.35	2.25 ^b	92.69	83.81
control	20.00	21.25	---	23.00	---	25.25	---	30.25 ^c	---	---
2022										
Bancoron	19.00	---	---	9.00	60.78	4.50	82.29	2.00 ^a	93.18	78.75
Benadryl	19.50	4.75	76.84	---	---	3.75	85.62	1.75 ^a	94.19	85.55
Salinger super	19.25	4.5	77.77	---	---	3.25	87.37	1.50 ^a	94.95	86.61
Control	19.25	20.25	---	23.25	---	25.75	---	29.75 ^b	---	---

*The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the mean followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

Table (3): Reduction in *Chrysoperla carnea* larvae due to applied lufenuron and conventional insecticides in 2021 and 2022 seasons.

Compound	Before spray	After one day		Three days		7 days		10 days		Overall mean
	M.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.*	Red.	
2021										
Bancoron	8.25	---	---	7.5	17.61	7.5	22.45	7.75 ^a	30.14	23.40
Benadryl	8.00	0.75	90.93	---	---	1.25	86.67	1.25 ^b	88.38	88.66
Salinger super	8.00	0.50	93.95	---	---	0.75	92.00	1.00 ^b	90.70	92.21
Control	7.25	7.50	---	8.00	---	8.50	---	9.75 ^c	---	---
2022										
Bancoron	7.5	---	---	7.25	11.86	7.00	19.62	7.25 ^a	26.91	19.46
Benadryl	7.25	1.00	87.04	---	---	0.75	91.09	0.5 ^b	94.78	90.97
Salinger super	7.5	1.25	84.34	---	---	1.25	85.64	1.5 ^c	84.87	84.95
Control	7.75	8.25	---	8.50	---	9.00	---	10.25 ^d	---	---

*The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the mean followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

2. Root and sugar yield:

Table (4) indicates insignificant differences between treated plots with lufenuron insecticide and conventional ones in the root and sugar yield of sugar beet during the two seasons. Data clarifies those significant differences between the treated plots and untreated ones (Control). These insignificant differences because

lufenuron killed the larvae in sufficient percentages. In addition, lufenuron does not affect the population of the predator *C. carnea* in high percentages in comparison with conventional insecticides.

Table (4): Impact of certain insecticides against *Spodoptera littoralis* on root and sugar yield.

Treatment	2021 season				
	Root weight (kg/168m ²)		Root yield (ton/fed)	Sucrose %	Sugar yield (ton/fed)
	Total	Mean			
Bancoron	910	227.50 ^a	21.67 ^a	16.10	3.49 ^a
Benadryl	915	228.75 ^a	21.79 ^a	16.23	3.54 ^a
Salinger	916	229.00 ^a	21.81 ^a	16.15	3.52 ^a
Control	501	125.25 ^b	11.93 ^b	11.00	1.31 ^b
2022 season					
Bancoron	914	228.50 ^a	21.76 ^a	16.00	3.48 ^a
Benadryl	916	229.00 ^a	21.81 ^a	16.20	3.53 ^a
Salinger	916	229.00 ^a	21.81 ^a	16.19	3.53 ^a
Control	520	130.00 ^b	12.38 ^b	12.11	1.50 ^b

*The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the mean followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

In conclusion, these results proved that lufenuron insecticides besides *C. carnea* as a major predator were able to suppress *S. littoralis* population and enhance sugar beet productivity.

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Effectiveness of biocides for controlling aphids (Hemiptera: Aphididae) without decreasing insect predator population in Egyptian sugar beet fields

Hend, A. A. Gad and Walaa, B. F. Badawy

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted at the experimental farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt, seasonally during 2021/ 2022 and 2022/ 2023. The field study evaluated the efficiency of biocide, Biosiana® 2.5 wp and Billy®, Basudin® as conventional insecticides against aphids and their side effects on insect predators. The results showed that the mean reduction in the populations of aphids caused by Biosiana was 73.07 and 70.68% in the first and second seasons, respectively. Applications of the conventional insecticide, Billy resulted in 71.57 and 71.15 % mean population reduction in the two seasons, respectively. Also, 67.11 and 72.94 % mean reduction in aphid populations during the two seasons, respectively, for Basudin®. In such concern, the insect predators associated with aphid numbers, the application of Biosiana reduced the densities of insect predators by 25.93 and 24.0 % in the two seasons, respectively. While the density of insect predator plots treated with conventional insecticides was reduced by 79.66 and 79.60 % for Billy® in the two seasons, 74.87 and 78.72 % for Basudin® during the two seasons. These findings indicate that Basudin® reduces the population of aphid high percentages, while not significantly reducing densities of insect predators, as seen in plots treated with conventional insecticides. In addition, this study surveyed four species of aphids [*Aphis craccivora* (Koch), *Aphis gossypii* (Glover), *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) and *Schizaphis graminum* (Rondani) (Hemiptera: Aphididae)]. Moreover, surveying 9 predatory insect species, belonging to 7 families and four orders. In conclusion, Biosiana® can be used as a tactic in a successful integrated pest management program for aphid species in sugar beet fields, thereby reducing reliance on conventional insecticides.

Introduction

Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) is considered one of the most important sugar crops worldwide. In Egypt, it is the first

important sugar crop before sugar cane for sugar production (Hellal *et al.*, 2009). The Egyptian agricultural policy depends on reducing the gap between sugar production

and consumption by encouraging the farmers to increase the cultivated area of sugar beet (Afifi, 2001).

In 2021 / 2022 season, the total area cultivated with sugar beet reached 700 thousand feddans in Egypt that produce more than 1.6 million tons of sugar. Sugar beet is liable to be attacked by many destructive insect pests during its different growing stages. So, many authors were attracted to study a group of insect pests that cause serious problems for farmers and cause reductions in sugar beet yield (Roots and sugar percent %) (Bassyouny and Khalafalla, 1996; Ebieda, 1997 and El-Dessouki, 2019). The overall loss resulting from insect pest infestations in sugar beet crops range between 8.2 to 12.4 % (Kolbe, 1967). The piercing sucking insects such as aphids are considered among the economic pests of sugar beet plants at the present time (Frag *et al.*, 1998; Al-Habshy *et al.*, 2014; Bazazo *et al.*, 2017 and Khalifa, 2017 and 2018) causing significant damage by piercing and sucking the plant sap and indirect damage by transmission of many virus diseases from plant to another, also can substantially decrease crop yields (Frédéric *et al.*, 2022 and Anabelle *et al.*, 2023). In Czech Republic, Muska (2007) mentioned that aphids belong to the most important pests of sugar beet crops. The green peach aphid *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) causes damage.

By sucking and transmission of virus diseases. Damage is evident in all sugar beet growing regions in the Czech Republic. In Belgium, Albittar *et al.* (2016) reported that *M. persicae* is responsible for losses in yield and viral diseases. In Egyptian fields, Sherief *et al.* (2013) found that *M. persicae* recorded one peak of abundance in the first season. It was recorded on the 2nd week of February and represented by 2945 indiv. / 50 plants. While, in the second season, one peak of abundance was also recorded on the 3rd week of February

and represented by 3089 insects / 50 plants. Moreover, Al-Habshy *et al.* (2014) mentioned that the seasonal abundance of *M. persicae* of the sugar beet crops recorded two peaks for *M. persicae*. The first one occurred in the 2nd week of December with 275 and 316 insects / samples for the two seasons, respectively. The second one was observed in the 4th week of January represented by 417 and 548 indiv. / Sample for the two seasons, respectively.

The previous results showed that *M. persicae* in addition to the presence of *Aphis craccivora* (Koch) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) recorded a total number of 3417 to 3590 and 94 to 104 insects / Plant samples for the two seasons, respectively. In addition, El-Dessouki (2014) found that in the first season (2010–2011), no special pattern could be obtained as regards aphids on sugar beet throughout different planting dates. Aphid populations were very high on the plants of Mid-Nov. plantation by Mid-Oct. and finally by Mid-Aug. plantation during 2011–2012. In such concern, Khalifa (2017) showed that the aphid population density was 26.17, 17.75 and 15.83 nymphs and adults / 25 sugar beet plants in August, September, and October plantation, respectively.

Concerning insect predators of aphids, many authors surveyed that coccinellidae, *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae); Carabidae, *Paederus alfieri* Koch (Coleoptera:Staphylinidae) , *Scymnus interruptus* Goeze (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Syrphus corolla* Fabricius (Diptera: Syrphidae) are dominating predators of aphids. They play an important role in managing aphids in sugar beet fields (Shalaby, 2012; Sherief *et al.*, 2013; El-Dessouki , 2014 ; Khalifa, 2017 and Al-Habshy, 2018).

Seni and Halder (2022) noted that using insect predators as a biological control agent is very useful in insect pest management. More than 30 families of predators in nature and among them, the Coccinellidae, Syrphidae, Anthocoride, Staphylinidae, Reduviidae, Carabidae and Formicidae are important agri-horticultural perspective. Aphids are devoured by various previous predators. Microbial insecticides are increasingly being considered environmentally friendly alternatives in comparison to conventional insecticides (Ramanujam *et al.*, 2014).

Also, El-Husseini *et al.* (2004) reported that microbial insecticide (Fungicides) is effective in controlling sugar beet insects. In addition, using neonicotinoid insecticides had a big role in protecting sugar beet from aphid infestation which is considered to decrease the loss of insects (Wagner, 2020; Barmantlo *et al.*, 2021 and François *et al.*, 2022).

So, the current study was done to determine the effectiveness of biocides on aphids, moreover their impact on insect

Table (1): Insecticides sprayed against aphids during the two seasons.

Trade name	Chemical class	Common name	Rate/fed.
*Biosiana® 2.5% WP	Biocide (fungi)	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> Bals. (1X10 ⁸ cfu)	500 gm
**Billy® 25% WG	Neonicotinoids	Thiamethoxam	125 gm
**Basudin® 60% EC	Organophosphate	Diazinon	1000 ml

*Biocides

**Conventional insecticides.

Results and discussion

In the current study, five species (Table 2) of aphids were recorded belonging

Table (2): Survey of aphid species inhabiting sugar beet plants during 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 seasons.

Order	Species	Family
Hemiptera	<i>Aphis gossypii</i> (Glover)	Aphididae
	<i>Aphis craccivora</i> (Koch.)	
	<i>Myzus persicae</i> (Sulzer)	
	<i>Schizaphis graminum</i> L.	

Various investigators demonstrated the danger of aphid species on sugar beet

predators in comparison with traditional insecticides.

Materials and methods

This study was conducted at a sugar beet field planted with Sahar cultivar on the 10th of October at Sakha Agricultural Research Station for two successive seasons: 2021/2022 and 2022/2023. Three treatments were used, and each treatment was replicated four times (3X4=12 plots), each plot measured 42m², moreover four plots as a check.

The insecticides tested against aphid populations infecting sugar beet crops are presented in Table (1). The number of aphids and insect predators was counted by visual examination on 40 sugar beet plants just before spraying and one, 7 and 10 days post spraying for conventional insecticides. Also, three, 7 and 10 days post spraying for biocide insecticide. Knapsack sprayer (20L volume) was used for spraying on 10th March in the two seasons. The samples of aphids were taken with a fine brush and put into vials containing alcohol 70%, after that transported to the laboratory.

to one family. The survey was carried out using a fine brush method.

crops during the three plantations. They cause direct damage by piercing and sucking

the sap of plants, consequently, reducing the sugar beet root weight and sugar content percentages. Also, they cause indirect

damage by transmission of virus diseases (Khalifa, 2018).

Table (3): Survey of insect predators associated with aphid species during 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 seasons.

Order	Family	Species
Coleoptera	Anthicidae	<i>Anthicus</i> sp.
	Carabidae	<i>Bembidion mixtum</i> Schaum
	Coccinellidae	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L.
		<i>Scymnus interuptus</i> Goeze
		<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> Reiche
Staphylinidae	<i>Paedrus alferii</i> L.	
Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp.
Diptera	Syrphidae	<i>Syrphus corolla</i> F.
Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> Steph.

Table (3) indicated that the survey revealed the occurrence of nine predatory insect species, belonging to seven families and four orders. Numerous authors showed that these previous predators are fed upon

aphids in Egyptian sugar beet fields. These predators are important agents in controlling aphids (Shalaby, 2012 and Al-Habshy, 2018).

Table (4): Effect of different insecticides on aphid populations under field conditions, during 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 seasons.

2021/ 2022										
Insecticides	Before M.	After								Overall mean of reduction
		1		3		7		10		
		M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	
Biosiana®	20.00	-----	-----	10.0	53.52	4.75	78.67	3.0	87.11	73.07 ^a
Billy®	20.25	11.5	45.28	-----	-----	4.5	80.05	2.5	89.39	71.57 ^b
Basudin®	20.25	12.5	40.52	-----	-----	5.25	76.72	3.75	84.09	67.11 ^c
Check	19.75	20.5	-----	21.25	-----	22.0	-----	23.0	-----	-----
2022 / 2023										
Biosiana®	20.5	-----	-----	10.5	51.65	5.5	79.76	3.75	84.63	70.68 ^a
Billy®	20.75	10.75	49.39	-----	-----	5.0	78.23	3.5	85.83	71.15 ^a
Basudin®	20.75	10.5	50.57	-----	-----	4.5	80.41	3.0	87.85	72.94 ^a
Check	21.00	21.5	-----	22.25	-----	23.25	-----	25.0	-----	-----

The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the mean followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

According to aphid populations reduction percentages (Table 4), there were statistically significant differences among the means of the applied treatments. The overall reduction means of aphids due to Biosiana® were compared to Billy and Basudin applications, respectively, during the two seasons. The overall mean of reductions during 2021/2022 season for Biosiana was 73.07 followed by Billy and Basudin by

decreasing 71.57 and 67.11, respectively. While in the second season 2022/2023 the pesticide Basudin had an overall reduction reach of 72.94 followed by Billy and Biosiana with 71.15 and 70.68, respectively.

These results may be near to the results of Anabelle *et al.* (2023) which conducted that spinetoram and flonicamid caused a reduction in aphid numbers, while biopesticide was less effective.

Table (5): Impact of certain insecticides on insect predators associated with aphid species under field conditions, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 seasons.

Insecticides	Before	After								Overall mean of reduction
	M.	1		3		7		10		
		M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	M.	Red.	
2021 / 2022										
Biosiana®	7.5	-----	-----	6.75	18.43	6.5	23.83	6.0	35.55	25.93 ^a
Billy®	7.5	1.5	80.66	-----	-----	1.75	79.49	2.25	78.83	79.66 ^b
Basudin®	7.25	1.75	76.66	-----	-----	2.0	75.75	2.5	72.22	74.87 ^c
Check	7.25	7.5	-----	8.0	-----	8.25	-----	9.0	-----	-----
2022 / 2023										
Biosiana®	6.50	-----	-----	6.00	17.24	5.50	26.66	5.75	28.12	24.00 ^a
Billy®	6.75	1.25	82.16	-----	-----	1.50	80.74	2.00	75.92	79.60 ^b
Basudin®	6.75	1.00	85.73	-----	-----	1.75	77.53	2.25	72.91	78.72 ^b
Check	6.50	6.75	-----	7.25	-----	7.50	-----	8.00	-----	-----

The Duncan test at level of 5% probability was applied, the mean followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

Concerning the insect predators in Table (5), Biosiana is safer than these predators in comparison with conventional insecticides (25.93 and 24.00 %) for Biosiana. In addition to, (79.66 and 79.60 %) for Billy, (74.87 and 78.72 %) for Basudin in the seasons, respectively. The results demonstrated that Biosiana is effective against aphid populations, moreover very safe for insect predators in comparison with conventional insecticides.

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Histological and biochemical studies of fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* on adults of the glassy clover snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) and the green peach aphid insect *Myzus persicae* (Hemiptera: Aphididae)

Noha, Lokma; Farag, M. F. N. G. and Asmaa, M. A. El-Sayd

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

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Abstract

Fungus is thinking about promising biological pest control. These papers, focus on changes in the activity of amylase and invertase enzymes in adults of *Monacha cartusiana* Müller (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) snail and *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) aphid treated with fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* compared with control utilizing the dipping technique. The highest concentration 10^8 spore/ml showed a very high decrease in amylase and invertase enzymes which caused the highest reduction after one day, three days and seven days of treatment compared to the control recording (-50.12, - 40.30, -24.96 %) and (-48.01, -33.40, -12.73 %) of amylase enzyme (-29.73, - 39.94, -51.42 %) and (-25.48, -38.91, -54.16 %) of invertase enzyme of tested snail and aphid, respectively. Histological studies were conducted on digestive glands in adults of *M. cartusiana* snails to recognize the fine structure of digestive gland in the two healthy and infected snails treated to 10^8 spore/ml after five days of treatment with tested fungus. The digestive gland lost its normal appearance, became degenerated and more vacuolated. The lumina of the tubules appeared more branched shape than those of the normal. The digestive cells became swollen, and the outer tubular membranes of some tubules are damaged. Also, histological studies of treated aphids showed much disinformation in their tissues and showed fungal growth inside the aphid body compared with untreated aphids with natural tissues with perfect cuticles divided into epicuticle and endocuticle. Finally, *Trichoderma yunnanense* was identified by utilizing 18s rRNA and its accession OQ659412.

Introduction

The introduction of novel crops, the consolidation of agricultural production regulation, resulting expansion over human

trade, and the trend of species adapting to these altered settings have all been connected to an increase in pest problems (Barker, 2002). Terrestrial snails are thought to be the

most harmful pest in Egypt's stylommatophora (Heiba *et al.*, 2002 and Ali and Robinson, 2020). Also widely dispersed in the Egyptian Governorates were *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller, 1774), Mollusca, Gastropod Pulmonata, Stylomatophora, Helicoidae, and Monacheae. They are appeared in vegetable and fruit crops, orchards, decorative and medicinal plants (Shetaia *et al.*, 2009; Heikal, 2015; Kadry *et al.*, 2018; Shahawy, 2018 and Rady, 2019).

Likewise, one of the most dangerous insect species that causes financial losses in agricultural fields is aphids (Leclant and Deguine, 1994). Due to its vast host range and as a vector of numerous plant viruses, it is a serious pest. Therefore, synthetic chemical pesticides are generally utilized for pest control (Wang *et al.*, 2002). As one of the main causes of environmental pollution, chronic diseases in humans, and harm to most living things, attention is being devoted more and more to the use of synthetic chemical pesticides as a hazardous way of pest management. *Trichoderma* species are widely known for producing a wide variety of secondary metabolites, such as polysaccharides, toxins, and antibiotics (Gams and Bissett, 1998).

Additionally, strains from various species of this genus are frequently utilized in the bio control of fungi that cause plant diseases in soil (Samuels, 2006). Significant use in the sector is using entomopathogenic bacteria as biological control agents (Lacey and Shapiro-Ilan, 2008).

This study was striped to assay the effect of fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* on some biochemical activities and the histological structure of adults of the glassy clover snail *M. cartusiana* and the green peach aphid insect *M. persicae*.

Materials and methods

1. Tested animal:

Adults of the glassy clover snail, *M. cartusiana* were collected from fields

cultivated with lettuce at Sheeba locality, Zagazig district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt and identified according to the keys given via Godan (1983). The captured land snails were delivered right away to the Plant Protection Research Institute's lab in white linen bags. Healthy and similar snails were selected and kept in a glass terrarium filled with damp clay soil that was 75% of the water field's capacity. Snails were fed daily with lettuce leaves for two weeks before treatment for acclimatization.

2. Tested insect:

The green peach aphid insect *M. persicae*, was collected from several fields in the Sharkia governorate of Egypt, placed in paper bags, and taken to the lab at the plant protection research institute in the same governorate of Egypt. Individually, the studied insects were raised in a lab. at a temperature of 25 °C, relative humidity of 70 %, and a photoperiod of 12 hrs. (Ahmed *et al.*, 1999).

3. Tested fungus:

In the plant protection research institute in Sharkia Governorate, *Trichoderma yunnanense* was isolated from the green peach aphid insect, *M. persicae*, using the homogenization technique, followed by dilution plating of the homogenate on modified Czapek-Dox's agar medium oxoid (Goettel and Inglis, 1997). Cultures were protected on PDA agar slants at 4°C and subcultured every 15 days. Then it was purified and identified morphologically using a light microscope according to Domsch and Gams (1980), Bissett (1991) and Moubasher (1993). A Sequence of 18s rRNA gene of DNA of fungal isolate was done at animal health research institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt. Molecular characterization included the following steps as per the Tarini *et al.* (2010) protocol.

4. Preparation of inoculum:

T. yunnanense was used to prepare spore suspension at various serial dilutions. The spores were collected by rubbing the surface of seven days old plate culture of the tested fungus utilizing sterile distilled water containing a drop of tween 80 (Krutmuang and Mekchay, 2005). The suspensions using a haemocytometer 10^6 and 10^8 spore/ml.

5. Biochemical studies:

5.1. Preparation of samples for the biochemical assay:

After 1, 3, and 7 days post-treatment, samples of aphids and snails weighing 1gm were taken from the treated (10^6 and 10^8 spore/ml) and untreated (control) groups of aphids and snails. *M. cartusiana* snails had their adult mollusca shells removed. In tiny vials, samples are stored in the freezer until analysis. Using a Teflon homogenizer, the frozen samples of the studied insects and snails were diluted in distilled water to a volume of 5 ml for each sample. The soft tissues of snails and insects were measured, collected, and homogenized in distilled water at a ratio of 1:10 (w/v). According to Abd El-Haleim *et al.* (2006), the homogenates were centrifuged at 5000 r.p.m. for 20 minutes at 5 °C. The enzyme sources for the amylase and invertase enzymes were the supernatants of the studied snails and aphids. The method outlined by Ishaaya and Swiriski (1976) was used to measure the activities of the enzymes under test.

6. Histological studies:

6.1. Preparation of tested snail:

Two groups of adult *M. cartusiana* snails 30 each were used. Land snails in a group (1) served as control while those in group (2) were dipped in 10^8 spores/ml of fungus, *T. yunnanense* and treated lettuce leaves with tested fungus for 30 seconds. The digestive gland (Hepatopancreas) of treated tested alive snails as well as control after five days of application was dissected. The shell was broken gently utilizing a small hammer,

and then the soft specimen was quickly dissected in a saline solution, Hedon Fleig's saline solution (Lee, 1965).

6.2. Preparation of tested insect:

According to Khaleil *et al.* (2016), two groups of peach aphids (*M. persicae*) were infected with spore suspension (10^8 spores/ml) of *T. yunnanense*, while the other groups received water as a control. After being cultured for five days at 25°C and 70% R.H., the groups were then processed for light microscopy.

6.3. Light microscopy:

The digestive gland of tested snail and insect organs were quickly isolated and transferred directly into 10 % formalin, to overcome the problem of the immediate autolysis. The isolated tissues of snail and insect were fixed for about 24 hrs. in 10 % formalin. The fixed tissues were dehydrated and cleared by utilizing alcohol as a dehydrator and xylene as a clearing agent. Embedding in paraffin wax with a melting point of 55 – 56°C was followed. Sections were cut at 2 µm. The prepared sections were stained by using eosin-haematoxyline (Drury and Wallington, 1980). Stained sections were critically examined and some of the examined parts were photographed at different magnifications. Scoping slides were achieved using a light microscope of a Plant Protection Research Institute in Sharkia Governorate, Egypt.

Results and discussion

1. Molecular identification of the tested fungus:

Using the primers ITS1 (1) and (4), the PCR product of the studied fungus (*Trichoderma yunnanense*) was sequenced. Utilizing the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) program, Altschul *et al.* (1990) and Altschul *et al.* (1997), the resultant DNA sequences from the PCR were compared to the published sequences to see if any homologs to the Gen Bank data existed. The sequences of the PCR products from the

tested fungus were 99.63 % identical to the sequence of *T. yunnanense* Figure (1). The tested isolate's phylogenetic tree revealed that *T. yunnanense* was in the same position and was organized according to an evolutionary

distance matrix based on incomplete 18S rRNA gene sequences (Figure 2). Figure (3) showed that the sequence of the PCR products from the chosen fungus was highly homologous to that of *T. yunnanense* (99 %).

	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma sp. XD-2018b isolate YMF1.04629 small subunit ribosomal RNA gene partial sequence internal transcribed spacer 1 partial sequence 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma pseu...</i>	992	992	96%	0.0	99.63%	604	MH383059.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma yunnanense CBS 121219 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma yunn...</i>	992	992	96%	0.0	99.63%	599	NR_134419.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma yunnanense strain YMF1.01694 internal transcribed spacer 1 partial sequence 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma yunn...</i>	992	992	96%	0.0	99.63%	585	AY941823.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma lieckfeldiae CBS 123049 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma lieck...</i>	970	970	95%	0.0	99.08%	577	NR_138438.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma pubescens strain DAOM 166162 from USA 18S ribosomal RNA gene partial sequence internal transcribed spacer 1 partial sequence 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma pube...</i>	963	963	96%	0.0	98.71%	572	DQ083016.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma poronioideum BPI GJS 01-203 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma poro...</i>	959	959	96%	0.0	98.53%	578	NR_134446.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma pubescens DAOM 166162 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma pube...</i>	959	959	96%	0.0	98.53%	627	NR_077179.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma anisohamatum small subunit ribosomal RNA gene partial sequence internal transcribed spacer 1 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma anis...</i>	957	957	96%	0.0	98.53%	599	MH113926.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma insigne small subunit ribosomal RNA gene partial sequence internal transcribed spacer 1 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma insigne</i>	957	957	96%	0.0	98.53%	577	MH113925.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma cerebriforme BPI GJS85-245 ITS region from reference material	<i>Trichoderma cere...</i>	955	955	96%	0.0	98.35%	594	NR_134447.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma hamatum DAOM 167057 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma ham...</i>	952	952	96%	0.0	98.35%	625	NR_134371.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma paucisporum BPI GJS 01-13 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma pauc...</i>	952	952	94%	0.0	98.88%	535	NR_134360.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma hamatum rRNA genes and ITS1 and ITS2 DNA	<i>Trichoderma ham...</i>	952	952	96%	0.0	98.35%	614	Z48816.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma theobromicola CBS 119120 ITS region from TYPE material	<i>Trichoderma theo...</i>	950	950	93%	0.0	99.06%	533	NR_134359.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma theobromicola culture CBS:119120 strain CBS 119120 internal transcribed spacer 1 partial sequence 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma theo...</i>	942	942	93%	0.0	98.87%	530	MH863052.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Trichoderma strigosum strain DAOM 166121 from USA 18S ribosomal RNA gene partial sequence internal transcribed spacer 1 partial sequence 5.8S ribosomal RNA gene complete sequence and internal transcribed spacer 2 partial sequence	<i>Trichoderma strig...</i>	941	941	96%	0.0	97.81%	577	DQ083027.1

Figure (1): 18S ribosomal RNA gene of *T. yunnanense*.

Figure (2): Phylogenetic dendrogram of several fungal isolates accessions detected via average correlation cluster analysis based on 18S rRNA partial sequence.

T. yunnanense CBS 121219 ITS region; from TYPE material Sequence ID: NR_134419.1 Length: 599 Number of Matches: 1. See 1 more title(s) See all Identical Proteins (IPG) Range 1: 11 to 567 GenBank Graphics Next Match Previous Match Alignment statistics for match #1 Score Expect Identities Gaps Strand 971 bits (1076) 0.0 552/559(99%) 3/559(0%) Plus/Plus Query 2.

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CTCCGTTATGGGGTTCCTGCGGAGGGATCATTACCGAGTTTACAACCTCCCAAACCCAATG 61 ||||| || | ||
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          11          CTCCGTT--
GGTGAACCAGCGGAGGGATCATTACCGAGTTTACAACCTCCCAAACCCAATG 68 Query 62
TGAACGTTACCAAACCTGTTGCCTCGGCGGGGTCACGCCCCGGGTGCGTCGCAGCCCCGGA 121
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          69
TGAACGTTACCAAACCTGTTGCCTCGGCGGGGTCACGCCCCGGGTGCGTCGCAGCCCCGGA 128 Query
122 ACCAGGCGCCCGCCGGAGGAACCAACCAAACCTCTTTCTGTAGTCCCCTCGCGGACGTATT 181
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          129
ACCAGGCGCCCGCCGGAGGAACCAACCAAACCTCTTTCTGTAGTCCCCTCGCGGACGTATT 188 Query
182 TCTTACAGCTCTGAGCAAAAATTCAAAATGAATCAAACCTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGG 241
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          189
TCTTACAGCTCTGAGCAAAAATTCAAAATGAATCAAACCTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGG 248 Query
242 TTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCAG 301
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          249
TTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCAG 308 Query
302 TGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCGCCAGTATTCTGGCGGGCATGCCTGT 361
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          309
TGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCGCCAGTATTCTGGCGGGCATGCCTGT 368 Query 362
CCGAGCGTCATTTCAACCCTCGAACCCTCCGGGGGATCGGCGTTGGGGATCGGGACCCC 421
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          369
CCGAGCGTCATTTCAACCCTCGAACCCTCCGGGGGATCGGCGTTGGGGATCGGGACCCC 428 Query
422 TCACACGGGTGCCGGCCCCGAAATACAGTGGCGGTCTCGCCGCAGCCTCTCCTGCGCAGT 481
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          429
TCACACGGGTGCCGGCCCCGAAATACAGTGGCGGTCTCGCCGCAGCCTCTCCTGCGCAGT 488 Query
482 AGTTTGCACAACCTCGCACCCGGAGCGCGGCGGTCCACGTCCGTAACACCCAACTTTC 541
|||||||||||||||||||||          Sbjct          489
AGTTTGCACAACCTCGCACCCGGGAGCGCGGCGGTCCACGTCCGTAACACCCAACTTTC 548 Query
542 TGAAATG-TGACCTCGGAT 559 ||||| ||||||| Sbjct 549 TGAAATGTTGACCTCGGAT 567
```

Figure (3): 18S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence; internal transcribed spacer1 and 1.5.8S ribosomal RNA gene, complete sequence; and internal transcribed spacer 2, partial sequence.

Large subunit partial sequence of 18S rRNA gene of DNA

```
TGGGGAATTCTACCTGATCCGAGGTCAACATTTAGAAAGTTGGGTGTTTTACGGACGTGGACGCGCCGC
GCTCCCGGTGCGAGTTGTGCAAACCTACTGCGCAGGAGAGGCTGCGGCGAGACCGCCACTGATTTCTGGG
GCCGGCACCCGTGTGAGGGGTCCCGATCCCCAACGCCGATCCCCGGAGGGGTTTCGAGGGTTGAAATGA
CGCTCGGACAGGCATGCCCGCAGAATACTGGCGGGCGCAATGTGCGTTCAAAGATTCGATGATCACTGA
ATTC
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Trichoderma yunnanense ENA13 Accession no. OQ65941

2. Biochemical studies:

The composition and operation of pest tissues are supported by carbohydrates. Amylase, trehalase, and invertase enzymes have a role in the digestion and utilization of carbohydrates by pests, controlling the metabolism of carbohydrates primarily Wyatt (1967). Enzymes like amylase and invertase are crucial for breaking down and using carbs as energy Naveed *et al.* (2009).

According to the data in Tables (1 and 2) *T. yunnanense*, a fungus, causing alterations in the activity of the enzymes amylase and invertase in the adults of the *M. cartusiana* snail and *M. persicae* insect as compared to the control utilizing the dipping technique.

The activity of amylase and invertase was decreased because of all treatments compared to the control. At concentration 10⁸ exhibited a very high decrease in amylase

enzyme which caused the highest reduction at different time intervals compared to control recording (-50.12, -40.30, -24.96 %) and (-48.01, -33.40, -12.73 %) of amylase enzyme (-29.73, -39.94, -51.42 %) and (-25.48, -38.91, -54.16 %) of invertase enzyme of tested snail and aphid, respectively. While concentration 10⁶ gave (-27.87, -15.55, -6.78 %) and (-31.76, -24.68, -5.01 %) of amylase enzyme (-2.76, -12.49, -22.12 %) and (-15.76, -26.29, -39.44 %) of invertase enzyme of tested snail and aphid, respectively.

Results showed a highly significant difference between the two concentrations of snails and aphids over time, except for seven days for the insect's amylase enzyme. Previous data agreed with those obtained by Khedr *et al.* (2005) discovered that five insect growth regulators (IGRs) had different biochemical effects on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) insect larvae in their second and fourth instars when tested under laboratory conditions.

Table (1): Activities of the enzymes (Amylase and invertase) change in adults of the snail *Monacha cartusiana* after treatment with the fungus *Trichoderma yunnanense* compared with control using dipping technique.

Tested Fungus	Conc. (spore/ml)		Amylase			Invertase		
			1 day	3 days	7 days	1 day	3 days	7 days
<i>Trichoderma yunnanense</i>	10 ⁶	SA	23.27 ^b	26.82 ^b	31.63 ^a	38.47 ^a	33.92 ^b	31.05 ^b
		RA%	(-27.87)	(-15.55)	(-6.78)	(-2.76)	(-12.49)	(-22.12)
	10 ⁸	SA	16.09 ^c	18.96 ^c	25.46 ^b	27.80 ^b	23.28 ^c	19.37 ^c
		RA%	(-50.12)	(-40.30)	(-24.96)	(-29.73)	(-39.94)	(-51.42)
Control		SA	32.26 ^a	31.76 ^a	33.93 ^a	39.56 ^a	38.76 ^a	39.87 ^a
P			0.0001 ***	0.0001 ***	0.0005 ***	0.0001 ***	0.0001 ***	0.0001 ***
L.S.D._{0.05}			2.58	1.64	2.60	2.59	2.56	1.21

SA = Specific activity as (ml glucose /ml)

RA% = (Relative activity %) = [(Treatment – Control) / Control] × 100.

Table (2): Activities of the enzymes (amylase and invertase) change in adults of *Myzus persicae* insect treated with fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* compared with control using dipping technique.

Tested fungus	Conc. (Spore/ml)		Amylase			Invertase		
			1 day	3 days	7 days	1 day	3 days	7 days
<i>Trichoderma yunnanense</i>	10 ⁶	SA	15.79 ^b	18.65 ^b	21.41	23.84 ^b	19.74 ^b	15.71 ^b
		RA%	(-31.76)	(-24.68)	(-5.01)	(-15.76)	(-26.29)	(-39.44)
	10 ⁸	SA	12.03 ^b	16.49 ^b	19.67	21.09 ^c	16.36 ^b	11.89 ^c
		RA%	(-48.01)	(-33.40)	(-12.73)	(-25.48)	(-38.91)	(-54.16)
Control		SA	23.14 ^a	24.76 ^a	22.54	28.30 ^a	26.78 ^a	25.94 ^a
P			0.0014 **	0.0009 ***	0.0899 ^{ns}	0.0003 ***	0.0054 **	0.0001 ***
L.S.D._{0.05}			3.99	2.83	2.60	1.99	4.90	3.27

SA = Specific activity as (ml glucose /ml)

RA% = (Relative activity %) = [(Treatment – Control) / Control] × 100.

After 2 and 5 days, the tested IGRs significantly boosted the activity of the trehalase, invertase, and amylase enzymes in both the 2nd and 4th instars.

Omar *et al.* (2006) studied the biochemical impacts of Chinmix, Spintor and Biorepel components on larvae of pink and spiny bollworms *P. gossypiella*, as compared to control. In comparison to the control, Farag (2012) found that all castor oil treatments of the *M. cartusiana* snail reduced the activity of the enzymes, amylase and invertase. Khaleil *et al.* (2016) reported that the biochemical analysis of adult cotton aphid treated with fungus, *Trichoderma hamatum* studied different quantitative changes in the amylase and invertase enzymes relative activities as compared to control. Farag and Sabry (2017) showed that *M. cartusiana* adults treated with used frying soybean oil have decreased amylase, invertase, and trehalase enzymes activity compared to control.

3. Histological studies

3.1. Histological observation in the digestive gland (Hepatopancreas) of *Monacha cartusiana* snail:

The digestive gland of normal snails Figure (4) is a lobed part of the alimentary canal. This gland has several tubules in each of its lobes. Each digestive gland tubule is surrounded by a thin layer of loose connective tissue which fills the intertubular spaces and contains few muscle fibers. The lumen or ductless tubules open into a collecting duct which opens into the stomach from one side and into the intestine from another side. Primary secondary lobe (Acini) is present. Each acinus consists of a single layer of hepatic and pancreatic cells (Hence the name hepatopancreas). Lumen opens into collecting ducts which pour their digestive enzymes into pyloric stomach, when compared to snails exposed to fungus, *T. yunnanense* at a concentration of 10^8 spore/ml after five days of treatment.

Figure (5) showed that the lumen of the tubules appeared more branched shape than those of normal. The digestive cells became swollen and more vacuolated. The outer tubular membranes of some tubules are damaged. The shapes of all cell types became more irregular, and the cell membranes were impaired in some digestive gland tubular epithelium. Snails stopped nourishment and wasted their appetite with very sluggish movement. The results agreed with those acquired by El-Said (2009) indicated that following oral administration of the three doses of Protecto, Biovar pesticides and *Aspergillus flavus* fungus against *M. cartusiana* the general architecture of the

digestive glands wasted its normal appearance.

The damaged acini in the treated snails contained narrowing in acinar lumen, atrophied acini and acini became study to each other with confused architecture acini, evanescence of glandular and calcium cells. Farag (2012) reported that following oral administration of castor oil compared to methomyl pesticide on *M. cartusiana* and *E. vermiculata* snails, the general architecture of the digestive glands wasted its normal appearance compared to control.

El-Said (2017) showed the effect of isolated *Streptomyces heliomycini* and Gastrotox pesticide on the histology of the digestive gland of *M. cartusiana* snail. Data examined different alterations in the digestive gland compared with the control.

3.2. Histological observation of the green peach aphid insect *Myzus persicae*:

After 5 days at a concentration of 10^8 spore/ml, the adults of *M. persicae*, both treated and untreated, underwent histological examination. This study's microscopic analysis of adult *M. persicae* revealed that the *T. yunnanense* spore suspension significantly deformed and disintegrated the aphid's body and tissues. It discovered the growth and colonisation of the fungus inside the insect. The examination using a light microscope showed different histological alterations between the treated and untreated adult peach aphids Figures (6 and 7).

An adult untreated peach aphid was depicted in Figure (6) as having a typical, undamaged cuticle that clearly distinguished between layers called the

epicuticle and the endocuticle. Additionally observed were normal adipose tissue, normal intestinal epithelial cells encircling the lumen, a normal salivary gland in its entirety, encircled by its membrane, and normal ovarian tissue containing an embryo. The basement membrane that encompassed all aphid organs in the haemocoel of the aphid as well showed normal and intact.

Furthermore, as seen in Figure (7), the body of the treated adult aphid exhibited several deformities. The basement membrane that surrounded the internal organelles of the green peach aphid and clearly appeared in the treated adult *M. persicae* reported disintegrating and disappearing. Similar findings reported by many researchers (Quesada *et al.*, 2006; Schneider *et al.*, 2013 and Gabarty *et al.*, 2014) used light microscopy to reveal numerous histological alterations in numerous aphids because of infection with various entomopathogenic fungi.

Hussein *et al.* (2012) and Schneider *et al.* (2013) indicated that the cuticle is disorganized, not differentiated within its epicuticle and endocuticle layers, and has developed black spots, mentioning a direct fungus attack on the insect defense system. Numerous cuticle abnormalities were observed after *S. littoralis* larvae were treated with five different strains of entomopathogenic fungi (Amer *et al.*, 2008). According to Alves (1998) and Schneider *et al.* (2013), the mycelium growth and the beginning of the fungus' sporulation process likely

caused physical damage to the host's cuticle. It also may have caused biochemical degradation. Gunnarsson (1988) demonstrated that the host's innate defense system is activated once it recognizes the invading fungus by changes in the cuticle basement membrane's characteristics.

The salivary gland of adult *M. persicae* under a light microscope lost its protective barrier and appear because of and distorted because of *T. yunnanense* treatment, the hind intestine epithelial cells of the treated insect's observations revealed deformation Figure (7). According to Schneider *et al.* (2013) and Alves (1998), the alteration in the host's cuticle is most likely caused by physical damage brought on by the mycelium growth and the start of the fungus's sporulation process. It may also be the result of biochemical degradation. El-Banna *et al.* (2012) investigated a variety of histological alterations brought on by bacterial and viral infection of cotton leaf worm larvae. Sowjanya *et al.* (2008) examined the ultrastructural responses of crude destruxin produced via *Metarhizium* sp. on the salivary gland.

The objectives of studies on fungus, *T. yunnanense* is to safe method for controlling of adults of the glassy clover snail, *M. cartusiana* and the green peach aphid insect, *M. persicae* which studied of changes in activity of amylase and invertase enzymes and histological studies in tested snail and aphid using dipping technique compared to control.

Figure (4): Section of the digestive gland of adult of *Monacha cartusiana* (normal snail) showing the lumina (L) of the tubules open into a collecting duct which opens into the stomach from one side and into the intestine from another side, digestive cells (D.C.), excretory cells (Ex.C.) and calcium cells (C.C.). (X100).

Figure (5): Section of the digestive gland of adult of *Monacha cartusiana* exposed to fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* at 10^8 spore/ml after five days compared with control using dipping technique showing changes of excretory cells (Ex.C.), calcium cells (C.C.), dilatation of tubule with a wide lumen, infiltration within the intertubular connective tissue digestive cells (D.C.), and the lumina (L) of the tubules appeared branched shape than those of the normal. (X100).

Figure (6): Light microscope micrographs of untreated adult *Myzus persicae* insect. epicuticle (Epcu), endocuticle (Encu), embryo(EB), lumen(L), mid gut (MG), salivary gland (SG), basement membrane (BM) and adipose tissue (ADT) (X100).

Figure (7): Light microscope micrographs of adult *Myzus persicae* insect treated with fungus, *Trichoderma yunnanense* (10^8 spores/ml) spore suspension after 5 days post-treatment. epicuticle (Epcu), endocuticle (Encu), adipose tissue (ADT), gut cavity (GC), fungus spore (FS) and vacuole (V) (X100).

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